

AIRBORNE
LABORATORY

FAAM Core Data Product

Release 24.6.0 (7b31701)

FAAM

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CONTENTS

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Summary	1
1.2	Tracability	1
1.3	FAIR Principles	1
1.4	NetCDF	2
1.5	Data access and archival	3
2	The Core Data File	4
2.1	Filename conventions	4
2.2	Dimensions	4
2.3	Global Attributes	5
2.4	Variable Attributes	7
2.5	Variables	9
2.6	Flags	14
3	Postprocessing Modules	17
3.1	AL52C0	17
3.2	AirSpeed	18
3.3	BBRFlux	19
3.4	BBRSols	22
3.5	BuckCR2	27
3.6	CPC	31
3.7	CabinPressure	32
3.8	CabinTemp	33
3.9	DryMach	34
3.10	ElectricFieldJci140	35
3.11	ElectricFieldZeus	36
3.12	GINWinds	37
3.13	GeneralEastern	38
3.14	Gin	39
3.15	Heimann	45
3.16	KippZonenPyrgeometer	46
3.17	Nephelometer	47
3.18	Nevzorov	50
3.19	PRTTemperatureUncertainties	55
3.20	PRTTemperatures	57
3.21	PSAP	59
3.22	RadAlt	61
3.23	RecoveryFactor	62
3.24	Rvsm	63
3.25	S10Pressure	65
3.26	S9Pressure	66
3.27	SeaProbe	67
3.28	SignalRegister	70

3.29	SolarAngles	70
3.30	TPress	71
3.31	TecoSO2	73
3.32	TecoSO2V2	74
3.33	TeiOzone	75
3.34	ThermistorV1Temperatures	76
3.35	TurbulenceProbe	78
3.36	TwoBOzone	82
3.37	WVSS2A	83
3.38	WVSS2B	84
3.39	WVSS2Calibrated	85
3.40	WVSS2RH	86
3.41	WeightOnWheels	87
3.42	WetMach	88
4	Flagging Modules	91
4.1	RosemountTempDeltaFlag	91
4.2	RosemountTempCloudFlag	91
4.3	CPCCloudFlag	92
4.4	NephelometerCloudFlag	92
4.5	WVSS2RHTemperatureFlag	93
4.6	WVSS2CloudFlag	93

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Summary

This document provides a description of the FAAM core data product, including a summary of the processing that takes place and a standard which describes the format of, and metadata associated with, the core data product.

1.2 Tracability

The code that produces the FAAM core data product is openly available on [GitHub](https://github.com/FAAM-146/decades-ppandas) at <https://github.com/FAAM-146/decades-ppandas>. Additionally, from software version *0.11.1*, the code is archived on [Zenodo](https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.5711136) with DOI [10.5281/zenodo.5711136](https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.5711136). This is the concept DOI, which points to the most recent release of the code; DOIs are also available on a per-release basis.

1.3 FAIR Principles

Data provided by FAAM are intended to follow the FAIR principles, introduced by Wilkinson et al., 2016 (<http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>). FAIR means that the data are **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. A full description of the FAIR principles is available at <https://go-fair.org/fair-principles/>. For convenience, these are reproduced in part below.

1.3.1 Findable

The first step in (re)using data is to find them. Metadata and data should be easy to find for both humans and computers. Machine-readable metadata are essential for automatic discovery of datasets and services, so this is an essential component of the FAIRification process.

- (Meta)data should be assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier.
- Data should be described with rich metadata.
- Metadata should clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe.
- (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource.

1.3.2 Accessible

Once the user finds the required data, she/he needs to know how can they be accessed, possibly including authentication and authorisation.

- **(Meta)data should be retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol**
 - The protocol should be open, free, and universally implementable.
 - The protocol should allow for an authentication and and authorisation procedure, where necessary.
- Metadata should be accessible, even when the data are no longer available.

1.3.3 Interoperable

The data usually need to be integrated with other data. In addition, the data need to interoperate with applications or workflows for analysis, storage, and processing.

- (Meta)data should use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
- (Meta)data should use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles.
- (Meta)data should include qualified references to other (meta)data.

1.3.4 Reusable

The ultimate goal of FAIR is to optimise the reuse of data. To achieve this, metadata and data should be well-described so that they can be replicated and/or combined in different settings.

- **(Meta)data should be richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes.**
 - (Meta)data should be released with a clear and accessible data usage license.
 - (Meta)data should be associated with detailed provenance.
 - (Meta)data should meet domain-relevant community standards.

1.4 NetCDF

The FAAM core data product is provided in the **netCDF** format. NetCDF (Network Common Data Form) is a set of software libraries and platform independent data formats which are designed to support the creation, access, and sharing of array-oriented scientific data. NetCDF is designed to be

- **Self-describing.** A netCDF file include information about the data it contains (i.e. metadata).
- **Portable.** A netCDF file can be accessed by computers with different ways of storing integers, characters, and floating-point numbers.
- **Scalable.** A small subset of a large dataset may be accessed efficiently.
- **Appendable.** Data may be appended to a properly structured netCDF file without copying the dataset or redefining its structure.
- **Shareable.** One writer and many readers may simultaneously access the same netCDF file.
- **Archivable.** Access to all earlier forms of netCDF data will be supported by current and future versions of the software.

NetCDF is extremely commonly used, and is almost ubiquitous within the Earth sciences. Unidata (<https://unidata.ucar.edu>) provide and maintain software libraries for accessing netCDF data using C, C++, Java, and FORTRAN. Third-party libraries (which are generally bindings or wrappers to the Unidata libraries) are available for Python, IDL, MATLAB, R, Ruby, and Perl, among others.

NetCDF files generally consist of four components:

- **Attributes.** Attributes are metadata which can be attached to the netCDF file itself (called global attributes), to variables, and to groups (variable attributes and groups attributes, respectively). Attributes may be textual or numeric; numeric attributes may be arrays.
- **Groups.** Groups (available since netCDF4) provide a method to encapsulate related *dimensions*, *variables*, and *attributes*. They can be thought of as somewhat analogous to directories in a filesystem.
- **Dimensions.** Dimensions specify the size of a single axis of a variable within a netCDF file. Common dimensions for geophysical data include time, latitude, and longitude, though they do not need to correspond to physical dimensions. There is no practical limit to the number of dimensions which may be defined in a netCDF file.
- **Variables.** Variables are named n -dimensional (thus associated with n *dimensions*) arrays of a specified data type. Variables may have zero or more *attributes*, which act as metadata to describe the contents of the variable.

A minimal example of accessing a 1-dimensional variable, *data*, along with its *units* attribute and a global *title* attribute from a netCDF file, using python, is given below. Note that the netCDF library, *netCDF4*, is not included as part of the python standard library, but may be installed using your system package manager, pip, or conda.

```
1 from netCDF4 import Dataset
2
3 with Dataset('somefile.nc', 'r') as nc:
4     title = nc.title
5     data_units = nc['data'].units
6     data_data = nc['data'][:]
```

Python software libraries to aid in accessing FAAM data are in development, and will be made available in due course.

1.5 Data access and archival

FAAM aim to process and make available a preliminary version of the core data product within 24 hours of a flight, although this may take slightly longer when on detachment. The preliminary file, indicated by the postfix `_prelim` in the filename will initially be made available to registered users through the FAAM website, where it will also be available in an interactive visualisation tool. The preliminary file is intended to be used for visualisation and initial analysis.

Once all of the variables in this file have been checked by a FAAM staff member, the data will be archived at the Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA; <https://www.ceda.ac.uk>). The archived version will not include the `_prelim` postfix, and having gone through QC, may differ from the preliminary file. Users can access the data by first registering as a CEDA user, and then applying for access to FAAM core data. The core data file is generally freely available, however access may be restricted for upto one year at the request of a project PI.

1.5.1 Usage License

FAAM data are licensed under the Open Government Licence (<http://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/>).

THE CORE DATA FILE

2.1 Filename conventions

The core file is named as `core_faam_<date>_<version>_<revision>_<fltnum>[_<freq>].nc`, where:

- **date** indicates the date on which the flight took place, formatted as `YYYYmmdd`, where `YYYY` is the four-digit year, `mm` is the two-digit month, and `dd` is the two-digit day.
- **version** indicates the version of the core file, formatted as `vnnn`, where `nnn` is a three-digit integer. The most recent version is 5 (`v005`), which this document applies to. It is important to note that older versions do not strictly follow the conventions outlined in this document.
- **revision** indicates the revision number of the data, formatted as `rn`, where `n` is an integer. Larger values of `n` indicate a more recent release. Where more than one data revision is available, the file with the largest revision number should be used.
- **fltnum** indicates the flight number of the flight, formatted as `xnnn` where `x` is a lowercase letter, and `nnn` a three digit integer.
- **freq** indicates the frequency of the dataset, formatted as `nHz`, where `n` is an integer. If not present, the file is at 'full' frequency, with the frequency differing between variables. Typically 'full' and 1Hz files are provided.

2.2 Dimensions

All variables in the core dataset are timeseries with the same start and end times, and with frequencies of 1 Hz or greater. There is only one time dimension, `Time`, with a length equal to the duration of the dataset in seconds. Variables which are recorded at 1 Hz will have `Time` as their only dimension. Variables which are recorded at higher than 1 Hz will be stored as a two-dimensional array, with `Time` as the first dimension and `spsNN` as the second. Here, the `NN` represents the frequency in Hz. For example, a 4 Hz variable would have dimensions `Time` and `sps04`, and would be stored as an $n \times 4$, where n is the length of the dataset in seconds.

The dimensions which may be included in the full temporal resolution core data file are:

- `Time` - An unlimited dimension whose length corresponds to the length of the dataset, in seconds.
- `sps02` - 2 samples per second. A dimension of length 2.
- `sps04` - 4 samples per second. A dimension of length 4.
- `sps10` - 10 samples per second. A dimension of length 10.
- `sps20` - 20 samples per second. A dimension of length 20.
- `sps32` - 32 samples per second. A dimension of length 32.
- `sps64` - 64 samples per second. A dimension of length 64.

2.3 Global Attributes

2.3.1 Required Global Attributes

- **Conventions** - The conventions followed by this data
- **acknowledgement** - The acknowledgement for use of this data. Should read: Airborne data was obtained using the BAe-146-301 Atmospheric Research Aircraft [ARA] flown by Airtask Ltd and managed by FAAM Airborne Laboratory, jointly operated by UKRI and the University of Leeds for FAAM data.
- **creator_address** - The address of the FAAM offices. Should read: Building 146, Cranfield University, College Road, Cranfield, Bedford. MK43 0AL. UK. for FAAM data.
- **creator_email** - The email address of the data creator, or a generic FAAM email.
- **creator_institution** - The institute responsible for the creation of the data. Should read: FAAM Airborne Laboratory for FAAM data
- **creator_name** - The name of the person or institute responsible for this data
- **creator_type** - The type of creator. Should be one of person, institution, position
- **date** - Date of the flight
- **date_created** - ISO:8601 date/time file created, ideally yyyy-mm-ddTHH:MM:SSZ. Equivalent to revision_date.
- **flight_date** - Date of the flight
- **flight_number** - The flight number
- **geospatial_bounds** - A well-known text representation of the flight envelope
- **geospatial_bounds_crs** - Coordinate reference system for geospatial attributes.
- **geospatial_lat_max** - Maximum latitude of the flight.
- **geospatial_lat_min** - Minimum latitude of the flight.
- **geospatial_lat_units** - The units for geospatial_lat_* attributes
- **geospatial_lon_max** - Maximum longitude of the flight
- **geospatial_lon_min** - Minimum longitude of the flight
- **geospatial_lon_units** - The units for geospatial_lon_* attributes
- **geospatial_vertical_max** - The maximum altitude of the flight
- **geospatial_vertical_min** - The minimum altitude of the flight
- **geospatial_vertical_units** - Vertical units associated with geospatial_vertical_* attributes
- **geospatial_vertical_positive** - Positive direction of geospatial_vertical_* attributes
- **id** - filename without extension, needs to be globally unique w/ naming_authority
- **institution** - The institute responsible for the creation of this data. Should read: FAAM Airborne Laboratory for FAAM data.
- **keywords** - A comma separated list of keywords from the GCMD
- **keywords_vocabulary** - Controlled vocabulary for keywords. Should read Global Change Master Directory (GCMD)
- **license** - The license for this data. Should read: UK Government Open Licence agreement - <http://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence>
- **metadata_link** - A link to a release of a controlled vocabulary of metadata attributes
- **naming_authority** - The authority responsible for naming this data. Should read uk.ac.faam

- `platform` - Platform name of the FAAM aircraft. Should read: FAAM BAe-146-301 Atmospheric Research Aircraft
- `platform_type` - Platform type: aircraft
- `project` - The project a flight was for. Expected to be of the form `<project_acronym>` - `<project_name>`
- `publisher_email` - The email address of the data publisher
- `publisher_institution` - The institution responsible for publishing data. Should read: CEDA
- `publisher_type` - Type of entity responsible for publishing data. Should be institution
- `publisher_url` - The URL of the data publisher. Should be <https://www.ceda.ac.uk>
- `references` - A list of references relevant to the file
- `revision_date` - The date this revision created. Analogous to `date_created`
- `revision_number` - The revision number of the dataset. Starts at 0, increments by 1 for each revision
- `source` - A description of the source of the data. An instrument where this makes sense, otherwise a description of how data obtained
- `standard_name_vocabulary` - A vocabulary of standard names. Expected to be a CF standard name table, e.g. CF Standard Name Table v78
- `summary` - A brief summary of the data
- `time_coverage_duration` - The duration of the data, in ISO8601 duration format
- `time_coverage_start` - The start time of the data in the file, in ISO8601 format
- `time_coverage_end` - The end time of the data in the file, in ISO8601 format
- `title` - A brief title for the dataset
- `uuid` - V3 UUID: MD5 hash of `id+date_created`

2.3.2 Optional Global Attributes

- `calibration_date` - Calibration date, where this applies to all file contents
- `calibration_information` - Calibration information, where this applies all file contents
- `calibration_url` - Permanent URI or DOI linking to calibration info, where this applies to all file contents
- `comment` - Comment about data
- `constants_file` - Name of external file providing input to processing software
- `creator_url` - Institutional URL or researcher ORCID URL
- `deployment_mode` - Mode of deployment. Should always be “air”
- `external_variables` - Blank separated list of variables used from an external file
- `history` - Logs modifications to file since production
- `instrument` - Where all data id from a single instrument. Currently freeform, controlled instrument vocab to follow
- `instrument_description` - Where all data are from a single instrument. Textual description.
- `instrument_location` - Where all data are from a single instrument. Location of instrument on aircraft
- `instrument_manufacturer` - Where all data are from a single instrument. Instrument manufacturer
- `instrument_model` - Where all data are from a single instrument. Instrument model
- `instrument_serial_number` - Where all data are from a single instrument. Instrument serial number

- `instrument_software` - Where all data are from a single instrument. Name of software deployed on instrument
- `instrument_software_version` - Where all data are from a single instrument. Version of software deployed on instrument
- `notes` - Notes on this data file. For more detailed info than comment
- `processing_software_commit` - Commit hash for processing software in vcs
- `processing_software_doi` - DOI of the processing software release, if available
- `processing_software_url` - URL pointing to processing software source code, if available
- `processing_software_version` - Version of processing software
- `project_acronym` - Project acronym
- `project_name` - Full project name
- `project_principal_investigator` - Name(s) of project PIs. Comma separated if more than one
- `project_principal_investigator_email` - Email address(es) of project PIs. Comma separated if more than one
- `project_principal_investigator_url` - ORCID URL(s) of project PIs. Comma separated if more than one
- `revision_comment` - Brief description of changes between revisions
- `source_files` - List of source files used in the processing of this data product
- `time_coverage_resolution` - Resolution of data, where this is uniform across the file
- `processing_level` - Processing level of data, where it is uniform for all data in the file

2.4 Variable Attributes

2.4.1 Required Variable Attributes

- `_FillValue` - The prefill/missing data value
- `coverage_content_type` - ISO 19115-1 code. One of image, thematicClassification, physicalMeasurement, auxiliaryInformation, qualityInformation, referenceInformation, modelResult, coordinate
- `frequency` - The frequency of the data. Where this is >1, will typically correspond to an spsNN dimension
- `long_name` - A longer, descriptive name for the variable
- `units` - Valid UDUNITS unit. Where a `standard_name` is given, must be equivalent to canonical units

2.4.2 Optional Variable Attributes

- `axis` - Axis for coordinate variables. Should be one of X, Y, Z, T
- `actual_range` - A length 2 array, of the same datatype as the variable, giving the maximum and minimum valid values
- `add_offset` - Offset for packing. Default is 0
- `ancillary_variables` - Optional in no ancillary variables, otherwise required. Ancillary variables e.g. flags, uncertainties
- `calendar` - Required for the time coordinate variable. Should be one of standard, gregorian
- `calibration_date` - Calibration date, where this applies to variable
- `calibration_information` - Calibration information, where this applies variable

- `calibration_url` - Permanent URI or DOI linking to calibration info, where this applies to variable
- `comment` - Comment about data
- `coordinates` - Blank separated list of coordinate variables
- `flag_masks` - Allowed flag mask values. Required for bitmask style flags
- `flag_meanings` - Blank separated list of flag meanings. Required for flag variables
- `flag_values` - Allowed flag values. Required for classic flags
- `instrument_description` - Textual description of instrument.
- `instrument_location` - Where variable is derived from a single instrument. Location of instrument on aircraft
- `instrument_manufacturer` - Where variable is derived from a single instrument. Instrument manufacturer
- `instrument_model` - Where variable is derived from a single instrument. Instrument model number
- `instrument_serial_number` - Where variable is derived from a single instrument. Instrument serial number
- `instrument_software` - Where variable is derived from a single instrument. Name of software deployed on instrument
- `instrument_software_version` - Where all data in the group are from a single instrument. Version of software deployed on instrument
- `sensor_manufacturer` - Similar to `instrument_manufacturer`, but where the item is more accurately described as a sensor
- `sensor_model` - Similar to `instrument_model`, but where the item is more accurately described as a sensor
- `sensor_serial_number` - Where variable is derived from a single sensor, similar to `instrument_serial_number`. Sensor serial number.
- `sensor_type` - The type of sensor fitted, where different sensor types may be used to produce the same measurement. A canonical example of this is the type of temperature sensor in the Rosemount housings.
- `positive` - Applies to vertical coordinate. Should be “up” if included
- `scale_factor` - Scale for packing. Default is 1
- `standard_name` - See CF standard names list. Should be used whenever possible
- `valid_max` - Recommended where feasible. Where both `valid_min` and `valid_max` make sense, `valid_range` is preferred.
- `valid_min` - Recommended where feasible. Where both `valid_min` and `valid_max` make sense, `valid_range` is preferred.
- `valid_range` - A length 2 array of the same datatype as the variable, giving minimum and maximum valid values
- `processing_level` - Processing level of variable data

2.5 Variables

Below is a list of all output variables which can be created during postprocessing, split into variables which will always be written to file if available, and those which are generally only used internally, but which can be written to file if requested. Note that some variables may be duplicated here. This indicates that the same output variable may be produced from two or more processing modules, depending on the fit of the aircraft. These will be mutually exclusive, so that variables will be unique in a dataset.

2.5.1 Written if Available

Table 1: Default Variables

Name	Long Name	Processing Module
ACLD_GIN	Acceleration along the aircraft vertical axis from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit (positive down)	<i>Gin</i>
ACLF_GIN	Acceleration along the aircraft longitudinal axis from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit (positive forward)	<i>Gin</i>
ACLS_GIN	Acceleration along the aircraft transverse axis from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit (positive starboard)	<i>Gin</i>
ALT_GIN	Altitude from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit	<i>Gin</i>
AOA	Angle of attack from the turbulence probe (positive, flow upwards wrt a/c axes)	<i>TurbulenceProbe</i>
AOSS	Angle of sideslip from the turbulence probe (positive, flow from left)	<i>TurbulenceProbe</i>
BSC_BLUU	Uncorrected blue back scattering coefficient from TSI 3563 Nephelometer	<i>Nephelometer</i>
BSC_GRNU	Uncorrected green back scattering coefficient from TSI 3563 Nephelometer	<i>Nephelometer</i>
BSC_REDU	Uncorrected red back scattering coefficient from TSI 3563 Nephelometer	<i>Nephelometer</i>
BTHEIM_U	Uncorrected brightness temperature from the Heimann radiometer	<i>Heimann</i>
CAB_PRES	Cabin Pressure	<i>CabinPressure</i>
CAB_TEMP	Cabin temperature at the core consoles	<i>CabinTemp</i>
CO_AERO	Mole fraction of Carbon Monoxide in air from the AERO AL5002 instrument	<i>AL52CO</i>
CPC_CNTS	Condensation Particle Counts measured by the TSI 3786	<i>CPC</i>
EXX_JCI	Raw data from the Fwd Core Console JCI static monitor, static signal	<i>ElectricFieldJci140</i>
EXX_ZEUS	Electric field measured by the Zeus instrument	<i>ElectricFieldZeus</i>
GSPD_GIN	Groundspeed from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit	<i>Gin</i>
HDGR_GIN	Rate-of-change of heading from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit	<i>Gin</i>
HDG_GIN	Heading from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit	<i>Gin</i>
HGT_RADR	Radar height from the aircraft radar altimeter	<i>RadAlt</i>

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Table 1 – continued from previous page

Name	Long Name	Processing Module
IAS_RVSM	Indicated air speed from the aircraft RVSM (air data) system	<i>AirSpeed</i>
IR_DN_C	Corrected downward longwave irradiance	<i>KippZonenPyrgeometer</i>
IR_UP_C	Corrected upward longwave irradiance	<i>KippZonenPyrgeometer</i>
LAT_GIN	Latitude from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit	<i>Gin</i>
LON_GIN	Longitude from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit	<i>Gin</i>
NEPH_PR	Internal sample pressure of the Nephelometer	<i>Nephelometer</i>
NEPH_RH	Relative humidity from TSI 3563 Nephelometer	<i>Nephelometer</i>
NEPH_T	Internal sample temperature of the Nephelometer	<i>Nephelometer</i>
NV_LWC1_C	Corrected liquid water content from the Nevzorov probe (1st collector)	<i>Nevzorov</i>
NV_LWC1_COL_P	LWC1 collector power	<i>Nevzorov</i>
NV_LWC2_C	Corrected liquid water content from the Nevzorov probe (2nd collector)	<i>Nevzorov</i>
NV_LWC2_COL_P	LWC2 collector power	<i>Nevzorov</i>
NV_LWC_C	Corrected liquid water content from the Nevzorov probe	<i>Nevzorov</i>
NV_LWC_COL_P	LWC collector power	<i>Nevzorov</i>
NV_LWC_REF_P	LWC reference power	<i>Nevzorov</i>
NV_REF_P	Reference power	<i>Nevzorov</i>
NV_TWC_C	Corrected total condensed water content from the Nevzorov probe	<i>Nevzorov</i>
NV_TWC_COL_P	TWC collector power	<i>Nevzorov</i>
NV_TWC_REF_P	TWC reference power	<i>Nevzorov</i>
O3_2BTECH	Mole fraction of Ozone in air from the 2BTech photometer	<i>TwoBOzone</i>
O3_TECO	Mole fraction of Ozone in air from the TECO 49 instrument	<i>TeiOzone</i>
P0_S10	Calibrated differential pressure between centre (P0) port and S10 static	<i>TPress</i>
P10_STAT	Static pressure from S10 fuselage ports	<i>S10Pressure</i>
P9_STAT	Static pressure from S9 fuselage ports	<i>S9Pressure</i>
PALT_RVS	Pressure altitude from the aircraft RVSM (air data) system	<i>Rvsm</i>
PA_TURB	Calibrated differential pressure between turbulence probe vertical ports	<i>TPress</i>
PB_TURB	Calibrated differential pressure between turbulence probe horizontal ports	<i>TPress</i>
PITR_GIN	Rate-of-change of pitch angle from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit	<i>Gin</i>
PSAP_FLO	PSAP Flow	<i>PSAP</i>
PSAP_LIN	Uncorrected absorption coefficient at 565nm, linear, from PSAP	<i>PSAP</i>
PSAP_LOG	Uncorrected absorption coefficient at 565nm, log, from PSAP	<i>PSAP</i>
PSAP_TRA	PSAP Transmittance	<i>PSAP</i>
PSP_TURB	Pitot-static pressure from centre-port measurements corrected for AoA and AoSS	<i>TurbulenceProbe</i>
PS_RVSM	Static pressure from the aircraft RVSM (air data) system	<i>Rvsm</i>

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Table 1 – continued from previous page

Name	Long Name	Processing Module
PTCH_GIN	Pitch angle from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit	<i>Gin</i>
Q_RVSM	Pitot static pressure inverted from RVSM (air data) system indicated airspeed	<i>Rvsm</i>
RED_DN_C	Corrected downward short wave irradiance, red dome	<i>BBRFlux</i>
RED_UP_C	Corrected upward short wave irradiance, red dome	<i>BBRFlux</i>
RH_ICE	Relative humidity wrt ice water, derived from corrected WVSS-II VMR and Rosemount temperatures	<i>WVSS2RH</i>
RH_ICE_CU	Combined uncertainty estimate for RH_ICE	<i>WVSS2RH</i>
RH_LIQ	Relative humidity wrt liquid water, derived from corrected WVSS-II VMR and Rosemount temperatures	<i>WVSS2RH</i>
RH_LIQ_CU	Combined uncertainty estimate for RH_LIQ	<i>WVSS2RH</i>
ROLL_GIN	Roll angle from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit	<i>Gin</i>
ROLR_GIN	Rate-of-change of roll angle from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit	<i>Gin</i>
SEA_LWC_021	Liquid water content from the SEA WCM-2000 probe, element 021	<i>SeaProbe</i>
SEA_LWC_083	Liquid water content from the SEA WCM-2000 probe, element 083	<i>SeaProbe</i>
SEA_TWC_021	Total water content from the SEA WCM-2000 probe, element 021	<i>SeaProbe</i>
SEA_TWC_083	Total water content from the SEA WCM-2000 probe, element 083	<i>SeaProbe</i>
SO2_TECO	Mole fraction of Sulphur Dioxide in air from TECO 43 instrument	<i>TecoSO2</i>
SO2_TECO	Mole fraction of Sulphur Dioxide in air from TECO 43 instrument	<i>TecoSO2V2</i>
SOL_AZIM	Solar azimuth derived from aircraft position and time	<i>SolarAngles</i>
SOL_ZEN	Solar zenith derived from aircraft position and time	<i>SolarAngles</i>
STATUS_GIN	Solution status from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit	<i>Gin</i>
SW_DN_C	Corrected downward short wave irradiance, clear dome	<i>BBRFlux</i>
SW_UP_C	Corrected upward short wave irradiance, clear dome	<i>BBRFlux</i>
TAS	True airspeed (dry-air) from turbulence probe	<i>TurbulenceProbe</i>
TAS_RVSM	True air speed from the aircraft RVSM (air data) system and deiced temperature	<i>AirSpeed</i>
TAT_DI_R	True air temperature from the Rosemount deiced temperature sensor	<i>PRTTemperatures</i>
TAT_DI_R	True air temperature from the Rosemount deiced temperature sensor	<i>ThermistorVITemperatures</i>
TAT_DI_R_CU	Combined uncertainty estimate for TAT_DI_R	<i>PRTTemperatureUncertainties</i>

continues on next page

Table 1 – continued from previous page

Name	Long Name	Processing Module
TAT_ND_R	True air temperature from the Rosemount non-deiced temperature sensor	<i>PRTTemperatures</i>
TAT_ND_R	True air temperature from the Rosemount non-deiced temperature sensor	<i>ThermistorVITemperatures</i>
TAT_ND_R_CU	Combined uncertainty estimate for TAT_ND_R	<i>PRTTemperatureUncertainties</i>
TDEWCR2C	Corrected dew point temperature measured by the Buck CR2 Hygrometer	<i>BuckCR2</i>
TDEW_CR2	Mirror Temperature measured by the Buck CR2 Hygrometer	<i>BuckCR2</i>
TDEW_C_U	Combined uncertainty estimate for Buck CR2 Mirror Temperature	<i>BuckCR2</i>
TDEW_GE	Dew Point from the General Eastern instrument	<i>GeneralEastern</i>
TRCK_GIN	Aircraft track angle from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit	<i>Gin</i>
TSC_BLUU	Uncorrected blue total scattering coefficient from TSI 3563 Nephelometer	<i>Nephelometer</i>
TSC_GRNU	Uncorrected green total scattering coefficient from TSI 3563 Nephelometer	<i>Nephelometer</i>
TSC_REDU	Uncorrected red total scattering coefficient from TSI 3563 Nephelometer	<i>Nephelometer</i>
U_C	Eastward wind component from turbulence probe and GIN	<i>TurbulenceProbe</i>
U_NOTURB	Eastward wind component derived from aircraft instruments and GIN	<i>GINWinds</i>
VELD_GIN	Aircraft velocity down from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit	<i>Gin</i>
VELE_GIN	Aircraft velocity east from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit	<i>Gin</i>
VELN_GIN	Aircraft velocity north from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit	<i>Gin</i>
VMR_CR2	Water vapour volume mixing ratio measured by the Buck CR2	<i>BuckCR2</i>
VMR_C_U	Combined uncertainty estimate for water vapour volume mixing ratio measured by the Buck CR2	<i>BuckCR2</i>
V_C	Northward wind component from turbulence probe and GIN	<i>TurbulenceProbe</i>
V_NOTURB	Northward wind component derived from aircraft instruments and GIN	<i>GINWinds</i>
WAND_GIN	Wander angle from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit	<i>Gin</i>
WOW_IND	Weight on wheels indicator	<i>WeightOnWheels</i>
WVSS2F_PRESS_U	Pressure inside {ins} sample cell {interp}	<i>WVSS2A</i>
WVSS2F_VMR_C	Calibrated volume mixing ratio from WVSS2F	<i>WVSS2Calibrated</i>
WVSS2F_VMR_C_CU	Uncertainty estimate for calibrated volume mixing ratio from WVSS2F	<i>WVSS2Calibrated</i>
WVSS2F_VMR_U	Water Vapour Measurement from {ins} {interp}	<i>WVSS2A</i>
WVSS2R_PRESS_U	Pressure inside {ins} sample cell {interp}	<i>WVSS2B</i>
WVSS2R_VMR_U	Water Vapour Measurement from {ins} {interp}	<i>WVSS2B</i>

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Table 1 – continued from previous page

Name	Long Name	Processing Module
W_C	Vertical wind component from turbulence probe and GIN	<i>TurbulenceProbe</i>

2.5.2 Used internally

Table 2: Default Variables

Name	Long Name	Processing Module
ETA_DI	Variable recovery factor for deiced Rosemount housing	<i>RecoveryFactor</i>
ETA_DI_CU	Uncertainty in recovery factor for non-deiced Rosemount housing	<i>RecoveryFactor</i>
ETA_ND	Variable recovery factor for non-deiced Rosemount housing	<i>RecoveryFactor</i>
ETA_ND_CU	Uncertainty in recovery factor for deiced Rosemount housing	<i>RecoveryFactor</i>
IAT_DI_R	Indicated air temperature from the Rosemount deiced temperature sensor	<i>PRTTemperatures</i>
IAT_DI_R	Indicated air temperature from the Rosemount deiced temperature sensor	<i>ThermistorVITemperatures</i>
IAT_DI_R_CU	Combined uncertainty estimate for IAT_DI_R	<i>PRTTemperatureUncertainties</i>
IAT_ND_R	Indicated air temperature from the Rosemount non-deiced temperature sensor	<i>PRTTemperatures</i>
IAT_ND_R	Indicated air temperature from the Rosemount non-deiced temperature sensor	<i>ThermistorVITemperatures</i>
IAT_ND_R_CU	Combined uncertainty estimate for IAT_ND_R	<i>PRTTemperatureUncertainties</i>
LIRS	LWR I/R SIGNAL	<i>BBRSols</i>
LIRT	LWR I/R TEMP	<i>BBRSols</i>
LIRZ	LWR I/R ZERO	<i>BBRSols</i>
LP1S	LWR VIS CLR SIG	<i>BBRSols</i>
LP1T	LWR VIS CLR TEMP	<i>BBRSols</i>
LP1Z	LWR VIS CLR ZERO	<i>BBRSols</i>
LP2S	LWR VIS RED SIG	<i>BBRSols</i>
LP2T	LWR VIS RED TEMP	<i>BBRSols</i>
LP2Z	LWR VIS RED ZERO	<i>BBRSols</i>
MACH	Moist air Mach derived from WVSS-II(F) and RVSM	<i>WetMach</i>
MACH	Dry air Mach derived from and RVSM	<i>DryMach</i>
MACH_CU	Uncertainty estimate for moist-air Mach	<i>WetMach</i>
MACH_CU	Uncertainty estimate for MACH	<i>DryMach</i>
NV_CLEAR_AIR_MASK	Clear air mask based on Nevzorov Total Water power variance	<i>Nevzorov</i>
P9_STAT_U	Static pressure from S9 fuselage ports, uncorrected	<i>S9Pressure</i>
SH_GAMMA	Ratio of specific heats at constant pressure and constant pressure	<i>WetMach</i>
SH_GAMMA	Ratio of specific heats at constant pressure and constant pressure	<i>DryMach</i>
SH_GAMMA_CU	Uncertainty estimate for SH_GAMMA	<i>WetMach</i>
SH_GAMMA_CU	Uncertainty estimate for SH_GAMMA	<i>DryMach</i>
SO2_TECO_ZERO	TECO 43 SO2 interpolated zero	<i>TecoSO2V2</i>

continues on next page

Table 2 – continued from previous page

Name	Long Name	Processing Module
SREG	Signal Register	<i>SignalRegister</i>
UIRS	UPP I/R SIGNAL	<i>BBRSols</i>
UIRT	UPP I/R TEMP	<i>BBRSols</i>
UIRZ	UPP I/R ZERO	<i>BBRSols</i>
UP1S	UPP VIS CLR SIG	<i>BBRSols</i>
UP1T	UPP VIS CLR TEMP	<i>BBRSols</i>
UP1Z	UPP VIS CLR ZERO	<i>BBRSols</i>
UP2S	UPP VIS RED SIG	<i>BBRSols</i>
UP2T	UPP VIS RED TEMP	<i>BBRSols</i>
UP2Z	UPP VIS RED ZERO	<i>BBRSols</i>

2.6 Flags

Every variable has an associated flag variable named `<variable_name>_<postfix>`, and referenced in the variable's `ancillary_variables` attribute, which provides some quality or situational information about the data in the variable. There are two different flagging strategies used in the core data file; the first is a value-based quality flag, referred to as a value-based or classic flag, and the second is a packed boolean representation. Flagging is largely automatic, other than the `flagged_in_qc` flag meaning, which indicates that in the opinion of the person performing the quality control, that data should be treated with caution. It is up to the user to decide whether or not to use data which has been flagged. If in doubt, users should contact FAAM for advice.

2.6.1 Value-based Flags

Value-based flags represent the quality of the corresponding data variable, with a flag value of 0 representing data which are presumed to be of sufficient quality. Larger values of the flag generally correspond to lower quality data, though this isn't always the case.

For example, consider a variable array with values

```
1 2 6 5 4 3 6 5 4 3 2 1 4 5 6 7 7 6 5 3 2
```

and its corresponding flag with values

```
0 0 0 0 1 1 0 1 1 1 2 2 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
```

To understand the meaning of these flag values, we can look at the `flag_values` and `flag_meanings` attributes of the flag variable, which may look like

- `flag_meanings`: `data_good minor_data_quality_issue major_data_quality_issue`
- `flag_values`: `0b 1b 2b`

We can see that there are three different flag meanings and three different flag values, and can deduce that a flag value of 0 indicates the data are considered good, a flag value of 1 indicates a minor data quality issue, and a flag value of 2 indicates a major data quality issue. A user may choose, for example, to eliminate data with a major quality issue. To do this, they would simply mask/nan the variable wherever the flag variable has a value of 2, leaving the variable array as

```
1 2 6 5 4 3 6 5 4 3 - - 4 5 6 7 7 6 5 3 2.
```

Value-based flags will have the same dimensions as their associated variable, and the following variable attributes:

- `_FillValue`: `-128b`
- `standard_name`: `'status_flag'` if the associated variable has no standard name, otherwise `'<variable_standard_name> status_flag'`
- `long_name`: `Flag for <variable_name>`

- `flag_values`: An array of the values that the flag variable can take. Typically runs from 0 to `<length of flag_meanings> - 1`.
- `flag_meanings`: A space separated string of the meanings of each of the values in `flag_values`.

2.6.2 Bitmask flags

While the value-based flags map the values of an array to a single meaning, bitmask flags allow the representation of a boolean array for every `flag_meaning`. This is done by mapping each flag meaning to an increasing power of 2, which allows the representation of every possible state of every meaning using values from 1 to $2^{\text{num. flags}-1}$. A value of 0 indicates that no flags are set, and is set as a fill value. In order to a bitmask flag it must first be unpacked. This adds to the complexity of using the flag, but makes flags much more powerful, so most variables in the FAAM core data product use bitmask flags.

For example, consider a variable array with values

```
1 2 6 5 4 3 6 5 4 3 2 1 4 5 6 7 7 6 5 3 2
```

and its corresponding flag with values

```
1 1 3 3 2 2 4 4 4 4 6 6 6 6 8 8 5 5 3 3 1
```

To understand the meaning of these flag values, we can look at the `flag_masks` and `flag_meanings` attributes of the flag variable, which may look like

- `flag_meanings`: aircraft_on_ground flow_out_of_range temp_out_of_range data_out_of_bounds
- `flag_masks`: 1b 2b 4b 8b

There are four meanings, with each associated with a value of 2^n with n taking the four values 0, 1, 2, 3. In the FAAM core data, flag values are guaranteed to be increasing powers of 2, thus the flag array can be unpacked simply by progressively right-bitshifting the flag array, and taking the result modulo 2. In python, this can be achieved with the following code:

```
# Note that we don't need to worry about using the flag_masks attribute, as it
# is guaranteed to be powers of 2 from 1 to 2^(n-1)
unpacked = {}
for i, meaning in enumerate(flag_var.flag_meanings.split()):
    unpacked[meaning] = (flag_data >> i) % 2
```

this would leave us with the following in `unpacked`:

```
{
  aircraft_on_ground: array([1, 1, 1, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 1, 1,
↪ 1, 1, 1]),
  flow_out_of_range: array([0, 0, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1,
↪ 1, 0]),
  temp_out_of_range: array([0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0, 0, 1, 1, 0,
↪ 0, 0]),
  data_out_of_bounds: array([0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 1, 0, 0,
↪ 0, 0, 0])
}
```

Bitmask flags will have the same dimensions as their associated variable, and the following variable attributes:

- `_FillValue`: 0b
- `standard_name`: 'status_flag' if the associated variable has no standard name, otherwise '<variable_standard_name> status_flag'
- `long_name`: Flag for <variable_name>

- **valid_range**: The valid range of values in the flag variable array. Should be 1b, $2^{(\text{number of flag_meanings})} - 1$
- **flag_masks**: An array of the values that the flag variable can take, which will runs from 1 to $2^{(\text{number of flag_meanings} - 1)}$.
- **flag_meanings**: A space separated string of the meanings of each of the values in flag_values.

POSTPROCESSING MODULES

3.1 AL52CO

p_al52co.py

Warning

This module deprecated for flights after 2021-01-12

Process CO concentration from the AL5002 instrument. The instrument provides counts, concentration, sensitivity, and zero. However, the sensitivity and zero step change after calibrations, which propagate through to the CO concentration provided by the instrument. To avoid post-calibration step changes, we assume that the sensitivity and zero drift linearly between calibrations, and interpolate across the step changes to produce smoother sensitivity and zero-offset curves. The CO concentration is then given by

$$\text{CO} = \frac{c - z_i}{S_i},$$

where c is the count reported by the instrument, z_i is the linearly interpolated zero and S_i is the linearly interpolated sensitivity.

After a calibration, data continue to be flagged for 5 seconds, to allow for calibration gasses to be flushed from the system. Where available, the state of the V1 valve on the Fast Greenhouse Gas Analyser (FGGA) is used to identify and flag span calibrations.

3.1.1 Outputs

- **CO_AERO**

- `_FillValue`: -9999
- `actual_range`: [`<float32: derived_from_file>`, `<float32: derived_from_file>`]
- `ancillary_variables`: CO_AERO_FLAG
- `coordinates`: `<str: derived_from_file optional>`
- `coverage_content_type`: `physicalMeasurement`
- `frequency`: 1
- `instrument_manufacturer`: Aero-Laser GmbH
- `instrument_model`: AL5002
- `long_name`: Mole fraction of Carbon Monoxide in air from the AERO AL5002 instrument
- `standard_name`: `mole_fraction_of_carbon_monoxide_in_air`
- `units`: ppb

3.1.2 Flags

Variables in this module use bitmask flags. Some, all or none of these flags may be applied to each variable. Interrogate flag variable attributes `flag_masks` and `flag_meanings` to find the flags for each variable.

- `aircraft_on_ground` - The aircraft is on the ground, as indicated by `WOW_IND`.
- `co_out_of_range` - The derived CO concentration is considered out of valid range.
- `in_calibration` - The instrument is currently, or has recently been, in calibration. Data should be disregarded.
- `no_calibration` - No calibration has yet been performed. Data should be disregarded.
- `counts_zero` - The instrument is reporting zero counts. This is most likely erroneous.

3.2 AirSpeed

`p_airspeed.py`

Calculates aircraft indicated and true air speeds. Mach number, M , is calculated from static and dynamic pressures (here p and q , derived as `PS_RVSM` and `Q_RVSM`, in processing module `p_rvsm.py`) using the standard calculation `sp_mach` defined in `ppodd.utils.calcs`:

$$M = \sqrt{5 \left(1 + \frac{q}{p}\right)^{2/7} - 1}$$

Indicated airspeed is then given as

$$IAS = V_s M \sqrt{\frac{p}{P_{std}}},$$

where V_s is the speed of sound at standard temperature and pressure, and P_{std} is the surface pressure in the ICAO standard atmosphere.

True airspeed is given as

$$TAS = T_c V_s M \sqrt{\frac{T_{di}}{T_{std}}},$$

where T_c is a TAS correction term, defined in the flight constants, T_{di} is the temperature from the de-iced temperature sensor, and T_{std} is the surface temperature in the ICAO standard atmosphere.

3.2.1 Outputs

- **IAS_RVSM**
 - `_FillValue`: -9999
 - `actual_range`: [`<float32: derived_from_file>`, `<float32: derived_from_file>`]
 - `ancillary_variables`: `IAS_RVSM_FLAG`
 - `coordinates`: `<str: derived_from_file optional>`
 - `coverage_content_type`: `physicalMeasurement`
 - `frequency`: 32
 - `long_name`: Indicated air speed from the aircraft RVSM (air data) system
 - `units`: `m s-1`
- **TAS_RVSM**

- `_FillValue`: -9999
- `actual_range`: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- `ancillary_variables`: TAS_RVSM_FLAG
- `coordinates`: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- `coverage_content_type`: physicalMeasurement
- `frequency`: 32
- `long_name`: True air speed from the aircraft RVSM (air data) system and deiced temperature
- `standard_name`: platform_speed_wrt_air
- `units`: m s-1

3.2.2 Flags

Variables in this module use bitmask flags. Some, all or none of these flags may be applied to each variable. Interrogate flag variable attributes `flag_masks` and `flag_meanings` to find the flags for each variable.

- `mach_out_of_range` - Either static or dynamic pressure out of acceptable limits during calculation of mach number.

3.3 BBRFlux

`p_bbr_flux.py`

Calculates the corrected fluxes from the upper and lower clear dome and red dome pyranometers.

Note

Prior to software version 24.3.0, the BBRs were incorrectly labelled as manufactured by Kipp & Zonen. This has been corrected to The Eppley Laboratory inc. from version 24.3.0 onwards.

The thermistors in the pyranometers have a characteristic non-linear temperature dependence due to the manufacturing process. If not corrected for, this can lead to errors in temperature of up to 1 °C. A quintic equation has been fitted to the manufacturer provided corrections for a range of temperatures, providing a correction between -50° C and 40° C to within ±0.07 ° C.

$$T_c = T + (\alpha_0 + T(\alpha_1 + T(\alpha_2 + T(\alpha_3 + T(\alpha_4 + T\alpha_5))))).$$

The polynomial coefficients $\alpha_0 \dots \alpha_5$ are hard-coded, and take the values

$$[-0.774, 6.08 \times 10^{-2}, 2.47 \times 10^{-3}, -6.29 \times 10^{-5}, -8.78 \times 10^{-7}, 1.37 \times 10^{-8}].$$

The flux for each dome, F_d , is calculated by subtracting a 10 second running mean of the zero from the signal. The flux is then corrected for temperature sensitivity using

$$F_{d_c} = \frac{F_d}{1 + T_c(\gamma_1 + T_c(\gamma_2 + T_c\gamma_3))},$$

where T_c is the corrected dome thermistor temperature, and γ_n are the first n values in the dome constants array.

A threshold value, $F_{\text{crit}} = 920 \cos(\zeta)^{1.28}$, is used to determine whether the dome is in direct or diffuse radiation, with fluxes above F_{crit} (or $F_{\text{crit}}/2$ for red domes) assumed to indicate direct radiation. This expression for F_{crit} approximates the 'German' equation (ref?) but is simpler and remains positive at low sun elevations. If the flux

is determined to be direct, then the upper radiometers are corrected for the pitch and roll of the aircraft (Ref: M/MRF/13/5):

$$F = \frac{F_{dc}}{1 - f_r(\zeta) \left(1 - c(\zeta) \frac{\cos \beta}{\cos \zeta}\right)}$$

Here, $f_r(\zeta)$ is the ratio of direct:direct+diffuse radiation, currently assumed to be 0.95 for all solar zenith angles, $c(\zeta)$ is a correction term for the cosine effect (Ref: Tech note 8, table 4). The angle between the solar zenith and normal-to-instrument, β , is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \cos \beta &= \sin \phi \sin \zeta \sin \psi \\ &+ \cos \phi \cos \theta \cos \zeta \\ &- \cos \phi \sin \theta \sin \zeta \cos \psi, \end{aligned}$$

where ϕ is the aircraft roll, ζ is the solar zenith angle, ψ is the ‘sun heading’, the difference between the solar azimuth angle and the aircraft heading, and θ is the aircraft pitch angle. Ref: Tech. note 7, page 10. Prior to this correction, platform relative pitch and roll offsets, determined through flying clear sky box patterns, are added to the instrument-derived pitch and roll. These are given as elements 4 and 5 in the flight constants for each dome.

3.3.1 Outputs

- SW_DN_C

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: SW_DN_C_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 1
- instrument_manufacturer: The Eppley Laboratory inc.
- instrument_model: PSP
- instrument_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
- long_name: Corrected downward short wave irradiance, clear dome
- standard_name: downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air
- units: W m-2

- SW_UP_C

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: SW_UP_C_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 1
- instrument_manufacturer: The Eppley Laboratory inc.
- instrument_model: PSP
- instrument_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
- long_name: Corrected upward short wave irradiance, clear dome

- standard_name: upwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air
- units: W m-2
- **RED_DN_C**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: RED_DN_C_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 1
 - instrument_manufacturer: The Eppley Laboratory inc.
 - instrument_model: PSP
 - instrument_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
 - long_name: Corrected downward short wave irradiance, red dome
 - units: W m-2
- **RED_UP_C**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: RED_UP_C_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 1
 - instrument_manufacturer: The Eppley Laboratory inc.
 - instrument_model: PSP
 - instrument_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
 - long_name: Corrected upward short wave irradiance, red dome
 - units: W m-2

3.3.2 Flags

Variables in this module use bitmask flags. Some, all or none of these flags may be applied to each variable. Interrogate flag variable attributes `flag_masks` and `flag_meanings` to find the flags for each variable.

- `roll_limit_exceeded` - The aircraft is in a roll exceeding the specified max roll limit of 7.0 degrees from horizontal.
- `low_sun_angle` - The sun is low relative to the axis of the aircraft, exceeding the maximum allowed limit of 80.0 degrees.
- `flux_out_of_range` - The calculated is outside of the specified allowable flux range [-20.0, 700.0] W/m2

3.4 BBRsols

p_bbr_sols.py

Converts the raw voltages on the BBR channels to physical values via a linear calibration, using coefficients defined in the flight constants. Each radiometer provides a signal, a zero and a thermopile temperature.

Required calibration coefficients are CALUP1S, CALUP2S, CALLP1S, and CALLP2S. The fourth character in each of these identifies whether the calibration is for an (U)pper or (L)ower radiometer, and the fifth and sixth characters indicate whether the calibration is for position 1 (P1) or position 2 (P2). The first two constants in each calibration array are n_0 and n_1 linear coefficients for the sensitivity, while the second two are the linear coefficients for the thermopile temperature.

3.4.1 Outputs

- UP1S

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: UP1S_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 1
- long_name: UPP VIS CLR SIG
- units: W m-2

- UP2S

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: UP2S_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 1
- long_name: UPP VIS RED SIG
- units: W m-2

- UIRS

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: UIRS_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 1
- long_name: UPP I/R SIGNAL
- units: W m-2

- UP1Z

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: UP1Z_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 1
- long_name: UPP VIS CLR ZERO
- units: W m-2
- **UP2Z**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: UP2Z_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 1
 - long_name: UPP VIS RED ZERO
 - units: W m-2
- **UIRZ**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: UIRZ_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 1
 - long_name: UPP I/R ZERO
 - units: W m-2
- **UP1T**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: UP1T_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 1
 - long_name: UPP VIS CLR TEMP
 - units: degree C
- **UP2T**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: UP2T_FLAG

- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 1
 - long_name: UPP VIS RED TEMP
 - units: degree C
- **UIRT**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: UIRT_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 1
 - long_name: UPP I/R TEMP
 - units: degree C
- **LP1S**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: LP1S_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 1
 - long_name: LWR VIS CLR SIG
 - units: W m-2
- **LP2S**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: LP2S_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 1
 - long_name: LWR VIS RED SIG
 - units: W m-2
- **LIRS**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: LIRS_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 1

- long_name: LWR I/R SIGNAL
- units: W m-2
- **LP1Z**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: LP1Z_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 1
 - long_name: LWR VIS CLR ZERO
 - units: W m-2
- **LP2Z**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: LP2Z_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 1
 - long_name: LWR VIS RED ZERO
 - units: W m-2
- **LIRZ**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: LIRZ_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 1
 - long_name: LWR I/R ZERO
 - units: W m-2
- **LP1T**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: LP1T_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 1
 - long_name: LWR VIS CLR TEMP
 - units: degree C
- **LP2T**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: LP2T_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 1
- long_name: LWR VIS RED TEMP
- units: degree C
- **LIRT**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: LIRT_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 1
 - long_name: LWR I/R TEMP
 - units: degree C

3.4.2 Flags

Variables in this module use classic, value based flagging.

- **UP1S_FLAG**
 - -128: data_not_flagged - A fill value. No flagging information has been provided
- **UP2S_FLAG**
 - -128: data_not_flagged - A fill value. No flagging information has been provided
- **UIRS_FLAG**
 - -128: data_not_flagged - A fill value. No flagging information has been provided
- **UP1Z_FLAG**
 - -128: data_not_flagged - A fill value. No flagging information has been provided
- **UP2Z_FLAG**
 - -128: data_not_flagged - A fill value. No flagging information has been provided
- **UIRZ_FLAG**
 - -128: data_not_flagged - A fill value. No flagging information has been provided
- **UP1T_FLAG**
 - -128: data_not_flagged - A fill value. No flagging information has been provided
- **UP2T_FLAG**
 - -128: data_not_flagged - A fill value. No flagging information has been provided
- **UIRT_FLAG**
 - -128: data_not_flagged - A fill value. No flagging information has been provided
- **LP1S_FLAG**

- -128: data_not_flagged - A fill value. No flagging information has been provided
- **LP2S_FLAG**
 - -128: data_not_flagged - A fill value. No flagging information has been provided
- **LIRS_FLAG**
 - -128: data_not_flagged - A fill value. No flagging information has been provided
- **LP1Z_FLAG**
 - -128: data_not_flagged - A fill value. No flagging information has been provided
- **LP2Z_FLAG**
 - -128: data_not_flagged - A fill value. No flagging information has been provided
- **LIRZ_FLAG**
 - -128: data_not_flagged - A fill value. No flagging information has been provided
- **LP1T_FLAG**
 - -128: data_not_flagged - A fill value. No flagging information has been provided
- **LP2T_FLAG**
 - -128: data_not_flagged - A fill value. No flagging information has been provided
- **LIRT_FLAG**
 - -128: data_not_flagged - A fill value. No flagging information has been provided

3.5 BuckCR2

[p_buck.py](#)

This documentation adapted from FAAM document FAAM010015A (H. Price, 2016).

For further details see the [FAAM Met. Handbook](#).

The core processed data for the Buck CR2 includes the mirror temperature and the volume mixing ratio of water vapour. Prior to September 2016, the water vapour pressure was calculated using using the parameterisation given by Hardy (1998), which is based on the ITS-90 formulations. In September 2016, the data processing was updated to use the Murphy and Koop (2000) parameterisation for water vapour pressure. The vapour pressure over liquid water is now calculated according to

$$\ln(p_{\text{liq}}) = 54.842763 - \frac{6763.22}{T} - 4.21 \ln T + 0.000367T + \tanh(0.0415(T - 218.8)) \left(53.878 - \frac{331.22}{T} - 9.44523 \ln T + 0.014025T \right),$$

valid for $123 < T < 332$ K. The vapour pressure over ice is calculated as follows:

$$\ln(p_{\text{ice}}) = 9.550426 - \frac{5723.265}{T} + 3.53068 \ln T - 0.00728332T,$$

valid above 110 K. The water vapour pressure inside the instrument, $p_{\text{H}_2\text{O,Buck}}$ is calculated using either equation 1 or 2 depending on whether a dew point or a frost point has been observed. Above 273.15 K, a dew point is clearly observed. Below 243.15 K, we can be confident that a frost point is being measured. Between 243.15 and 273.15 K, a dew point is assumed if the mirror has not been below 243.15 K since it was last above 273.15 K and it has been below 273.15 K for less than ten minutes. If the mirror temperature is within the supercooled water regime but has been below 243.15 K since it was last at 273.15 K, or it has been below 273.15 K for more than ten minutes, a frost point is assumed. The fact that these are assumptions is reflected in the measurement uncertainty, described below.

The vapour pressure is converted to volume mixing ratio, $r_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, as follows:

$$r_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = \frac{e_f p_{\text{H}_2\text{O,Buck}}}{p_{\text{Buck}} - e_f p_{\text{H}_2\text{O,Buck}}},$$

where e_f is the enhancement factor given by Hardy (1998) and p_{Buck} is the air pressure inside the instrument.

A corrected dew or frost point is calculated, which is slightly different to the mirror temperature, correcting for the difference between the pressure inside the instrument and the static air pressure outside the aircraft. The water vapour pressure outside the aircraft is

$$p_{\text{H}_2\text{O,outside}} = \frac{p_s r_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}{e_f + e_f r_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}},$$

where p_s is the static air pressure. A dew or frost point is then calculated using the Murphy and Koop (2005) parameterisation. Frost points are calculated using an equation given in the paper:

$$T_{\text{frost,outside}} = \frac{1.814625 \ln p_{\text{H}_2\text{O,outside}} + 6190.134}{29.120 - \ln p_{\text{H}_2\text{O,outside}}}.$$

In the absence of an equation to calculate dew point, a numerical solving routine is used to find $T_{\text{dew,outside}}$ from Equation 1.

The uncertainty associated with the Buck CR2 measurements have several sources

- The uncertainty associated with the calibration performed at NPL (where applicable). This is derived from the NPL expanded uncertainty and fit to a power law.
- The repeatability of the calibration. This is derived from the NPL calibration measurements of different dew points and fit to a power law.
- The response time of the instrument and the atmospheric variability. This is based on an assessment of the standard deviation of subsequent readings to give an indication of atmospheric variability.
- The uncertainty involved in the interpolation of data between calibration datapoints. This is a function of temperature, increasing below 233.15 K.
- The bias associated with the uncertainty about whether there is water or ice on the mirror between 243.15 and 273.15 K. This is calculated using a flagging scheme according to the temperature history of the mirror.

These are combined to produce one uncertainty value for the mirror temperature, which may be propagated through to the volume mixing ratio and the pressure-corrected dew or frost point. Note that prior to software version 0.10.1 the uncertainties are expanded uncertainties. From software version 0.10.1 onwards, the uncertainties are combined uncertainties, for consistency with other variables in the core dataset which have an associated uncertainty.

3.5.1 Outputs

- **VMR_CR2**

- `_FillValue`: -9999
- `actual_range`: [`<float32: derived_from_file>`, `<float32: derived_from_file>`]
- `ancillary_variables`: VMR_CR2_FLAG
- `calibration_date`: `<str: derived_from_file optional>`
- `calibration_information`: `<str: derived_from_file optional>`
- `calibration_url`: `<str: derived_from_file optional>`
- `coordinates`: `<str: derived_from_file optional>`
- `coverage_content_type`: `physicalMeasurement`
- `frequency`: 1
- `instrument_manufacturer`: Buck Research Instruments

- instrument_model: CR2 Chilled Mirror Hygrometer
 - instrument_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
 - long_name: Water vapour volume mixing ratio measured by the Buck CR2
 - units: ppmv
- **VMR_C_U**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: VMR_C_U_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: auxiliaryInformation
 - frequency: 1
 - instrument_manufacturer: Buck Research Instruments
 - instrument_model: CR2 Chilled Mirror Hygrometer
 - instrument_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
 - long_name: Combined uncertainty estimate for water vapour volume mixing ratio measured by the Buck CR2
 - units: ppmv
- **TDEW_CR2**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: TDEW_CR2_FLAG
 - calibration_date: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - calibration_information: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - calibration_url: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 1
 - instrument_manufacturer: Buck Research Instruments
 - instrument_model: CR2 Chilled Mirror Hygrometer
 - instrument_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
 - long_name: Mirror Temperature measured by the Buck CR2 Hygrometer
 - standard_name: dew_point_temperature
 - units: degK
- **TDEW_C_U**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: TDEW_C_U_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: auxiliaryInformation

- frequency: 1
- instrument_manufacturer: Buck Research Instruments
- instrument_model: CR2 Chilled Mirror Hygrometer
- instrument_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
- long_name: Combined uncertainty estimate for Buck CR2 Mirror Temperature
- units: degK
- **TDEWCR2C**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: TDEWCR2C_FLAG
 - calibration_date: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - calibration_information: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - calibration_url: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 1
 - instrument_manufacturer: Buck Research Instruments
 - instrument_model: CR2 Chilled Mirror Hygrometer
 - instrument_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
 - long_name: Corrected dew point temperature measured by the Buck CR2 Hygrometer
 - standard_name: dew_point_temperature
 - units: degK

3.5.2 Flags

Variables in this module use classic, value based flagging.

- **VMR_CR2_FLAG**
 - 0: data_good - Data are considered valid
 - 1: not_controlling - The instrument is not controlling on a dew point
 - 2: mirror_contaminated - The instrument is reporting contamination on the mirror
 - 3: in_balance_cycle - The instrument is in a balance cycle and not recording a dew point
 - 4: data_missing - Data are expected but are not present
- **VMR_C_U_FLAG**
 - 0: data_good - Data are considered valid
 - 1: not_controlling - The instrument is not controlling on a dew point
 - 2: mirror_contaminated - The instrument is reporting contamination on the mirror
 - 3: in_balance_cycle - The instrument is in a balance cycle and not recording a dew point
 - 4: data_missing - Data are expected but are not present
- **TDEW_CR2_FLAG**
 - 0: data_good - Data are considered valid

- 1: `not_controlling` - The instrument is not controlling on a dew point
 - 2: `mirror_contaminated` - The instrument is reporting contamination on the mirror
 - 3: `in_balance_cycle` - The instrument is in a balance cycle and not recording a dew point
 - 4: `data_missing` - Data are expected but are not present
- **TDEW_C_U_FLAG**
 - 0: `data_good` - Data are considered valid
 - 1: `not_controlling` - The instrument is not controlling on a dew point
 - 2: `mirror_contaminated` - The instrument is reporting contamination on the mirror
 - 3: `in_balance_cycle` - The instrument is in a balance cycle and not recording a dew point
 - 4: `data_missing` - Data are expected but are not present
 - **TDEWCR2C_FLAG**
 - 0: `data_good` - Data are considered valid
 - 1: `not_controlling` - The instrument is not controlling on a dew point
 - 2: `mirror_contaminated` - The instrument is reporting contamination on the mirror
 - 3: `in_balance_cycle` - The instrument is in a balance cycle and not recording a dew point
 - 4: `data_missing` - Data are expected but are not present

3.6 CPC

`p_cpc.py`

Reports particle counts from the TSI 3786 condensation particle counter. Counts are reported as-is from the instrument; this module only provides flagging information.

Note

Prior to v23.3.0, the CPC included flags for both sample flow and sheath flow. These have been combined into a single flag, and a cloud flag has been added, as CPC data are not valid in cloud. **The cloud flag is added by a separate flagging module.**

3.6.1 Outputs

- **CPC_CNTS**
 - `_FillValue`: -9999
 - `actual_range`: [`<float32: derived_from_file>`, `<float32: derived_from_file>`]
 - `ancillary_variables`: `CPC_CNTS_FLAG`
 - `comment`: Sampled through a modified Rosemount Aerospace Inc. Type 102 Total Temperature Housing.
 - `coordinates`: `<str: derived_from_file optional>`
 - `coverage_content_type`: `physicalMeasurement`
 - `frequency`: 10
 - `instrument_manufacturer`: TSI Incorporated
 - `instrument_model`: Modified Water Filled 3786 Condensation Particle Counter

- instrument_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
- long_name: Condensation Particle Counts measured by the TSI 3786
- units: 1

3.6.2 Flags

Variables in this module use bitmask flags. Some, all or none of these flags may be applied to each variable. Interrogate flag variable attributes `flag_masks` and `flag_meanings` to find the flags for each variable.

- saturator_over_temp - The saturator temperature is above 6 C
- growth_tube_temp_out_of_range - Growth tube temperature is outside the valid range [40.5, 49.5] C
- optics_temp_out_of_range - Optics temperature is outside the valid range [40.5, 49.5] C
- sample_or_sheath_flow_out_of_range - Sample or sheath flows are outside the valid range [270, 330]
- counter_saturated - Counter has exceeded its saturation value, 1000000

3.7 CabinPressure

[p_cabin_pressure.py](#)

Derives cabin pressure from a pressure transducer located in the core console. A polynomial fit, with coefficients provided in the constants variable `CALCABP`, converts DLU counts → transducer voltage → pressure.

3.7.1 Outputs

- **CAB_PRES**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: CAB_PRES_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 1
 - long_name: Cabin Pressure
 - sensor_manufacturer: Rosemount Aerospace Inc.
 - sensor_model: 1201F2
 - sensor_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
 - units: hPa

3.7.2 Flags

Variables in this module use classic, value based flagging.

- **CAB_PRES_FLAG**
 - 0: data_good - Data are considered valid
 - 1: pressure_out_of_range - Data are outside the valid range [650, 1050] hPa

3.8 CabinTemp

`p_cabin_temp.py`

Derives cabin temperature from a sensor located on the right of the core console. A polynomial fit, with coefficients provided in the constants variable `CALCABT`, converts DLU counts → raw → temperature.

3.8.1 Outputs

- **CAB_TEMP**
 - `_FillValue`: -9999
 - `actual_range`: [`<float32: derived_from_file>`, `<float32: derived_from_file>`]
 - `ancillary_variables`: CAB_TEMP_FLAG
 - `comment`: Should be considered a qualitative measure only, due to lack of calibration and proximity to the core console
 - `coordinates`: `<str: derived_from_file optional>`
 - `coverage_content_type`: `physicalMeasurement`
 - `frequency`: 1
 - `long_name`: Cabin temperature at the core consoles
 - `units`: degC

3.8.2 Flags

Variables in this module use classic, value based flagging.

- **CAB_TEMP_FLAG**
 - 0: data_good - Data are considered valid
 - 1: sensor_uncalibrated - Indicates that the sensor is considered to be poorly calibrated. Temperatures are to be considered qualitative.
 - 2: data_missing - Data are expected, but are missing

3.9 DryMach

p_dry_mach.py

This module calculate a dry-air Mach number using RVSM pressure measurements.

Dry-air Mach number, M , is given by

$$M = \sqrt{\left(\frac{2c_v}{R_a}\right) \left(\left(\frac{p+q}{q}\right)^{\frac{R_a}{c_p}} - 1\right)},$$

The module also provides the parameter SH_GAMMA, which is the ratio of specific heats at constant pressure and constant volume, along with uncertainty estimates for MACH and SH_GAMMA. The former is the combined uncertainty of the uncertainty in BAe report 127 and the uncertainty in gamma, while the latter is a constant and assumed to be 0.003, which is derived from the impact of neglecting humidity at the highest expected VMR of 35000 at 1100 hPa.

3.9.1 Outputs

- **MACH**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: MACH_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32
- long_name: Dry air Mach derived from and RVSM
- units: 1

- **SH_GAMMA**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: SH_GAMMA_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32
- long_name: Ratio of specific heats at constant pressure and constant pressure
- units: 1

- **SH_GAMMA_CU**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: SH_GAMMA_CU_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32
- long_name: Uncertainty estimate for SH_GAMMA

- units: 1
- **MACH_CU**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: MACH_CU_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 32
 - long_name: Uncertainty estimate for MACH
 - units: 1

3.9.2 Flags

Variables in this module use bitmask flags. Some, all or none of these flags may be applied to each variable. Interrogate flag variable attributes `flag_masks` and `flag_meanings` to find the flags for each variable.

- `aircraft_on_ground` - The aircraft is on the ground, as indicated by the weight-on-wheels indicator

3.10 ElectricFieldJci140

[p_electric_field.py](#)

This module reports the raw counts from the JCI static monitor on the core console.

3.10.1 Outputs

- **EXX_JCI**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: EXX_JCI_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 1
 - long_name: Raw data from the Fwd Core Console JCI static monitor, static signal
 - units: 1

3.10.2 Flags

Variables in this module use classic, value based flagging.

- **EXX_JCI_FLAG**
 - 0: `data_good` - Data are assumed to be valid and representative of the physical quantity measured
 - 1: `uncalibrated_counts` - Indicates this data is raw, uncalibrated counts from the DLU. Use with caution.

3.11 ElectricFieldZeus

`p_zeus.py`

Provides the electric field measurement from the Zeus instrument. No processing is actually performed, the data reported by the instrument is simply passed through to the output, with the addition of a flag.

ZEUS is a window mounted static mill created by the MetOffice OBR group. It uses a sensor designed by Dr John Chubb (JCI 140) made by Hearn Morley/Fraser Anti-Static and an Arduino Uno to digitize the analogue signal. It is fitted in SW1.

3.11.1 Outputs

- **EXX_ZEUS**
 - `_FillValue`: -9999
 - `actual_range`: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - `ancillary_variables`: EXX_ZEUS_FLAG
 - `coordinates`: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - `coverage_content_type`: physicalMeasurement
 - `frequency`: 1
 - `instrument_manufacturer`: Met Office OBR, Hearn Morley, Fraser Anti-Static
 - `instrument_serial_number`: 12230002
 - `long_name`: Electric field measured by the Zeus instrument
 - `units`: kV m-1

3.11.2 Flags

Variables in this module use bitmask flags. Some, all or none of these flags may be applied to each variable. Interrogate flag variable attributes `flag_masks` and `flag_meanings` to find the flags for each variable.

- `aircraft_on_ground` - Aircraft is on the ground, as indicated by weight-on-wheels

3.12 GINWinds

p_winds_gin.py

Calculates a horizontal wind vector from the aircraft true air speed, derived from the air data computer, and the speed and heading from the GPS-aided inertial navigation unit.

The RVSM derived TAS is corrected to account for a discrepancy with the turbulence-probe derived TAS according to

$$\Delta\text{TAS} = -(4.0739 - (32.1681M) + (52.7136M^2))$$

where M is the Mach number, given by

$$M = \frac{\text{TAS}}{(661.4788 * 0.514444) \sqrt{\frac{T_{DI}}{288.15}}},$$

where T_{DI} is the air temperature measured in the deiced housing.

The resulting corrected TAS may also be modified with a scaling correction, specified in the constants as GINWIND_TASCOR.

The eastward and northward components of TAS, TAS_u and TAS_v are given by

$$\begin{aligned}\text{TAS}_u &= \text{TAS} \cos(\theta - 90), \\ \text{TAS}_v &= \text{TAS} \sin(\theta - 90).\end{aligned}$$

Where θ is the aircraft heading, which may be corrected with an offset given in the constant GIN_HDG_OFFSET to account for any misalignment of the GIN to the aircraft axis. The horizontal winds u and v are then given by

$$\begin{aligned}u &= u_G - \text{TAS}_u, \\ v &= v_G + \text{TAS}_v,\end{aligned}$$

where u_G and v_G are the eastward and northward components of the aircraft speed, reported by the GIN.

3.12.1 Outputs

- **U_NOTURB**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: U_NOTURB_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 1
- long_name: Eastward wind component derived from aircraft instruments and GIN
- standard_name: eastward_wind
- units: m s-1

- **V_NOTURB**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: V_NOTURB_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>

- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 1
- long_name: Northward wind component derived from aircraft instruments and GIN
- standard_name: northward_wind
- units: m s-1

3.12.2 Flags

Variables in this module use bitmask flags. Some, all or none of these flags may be applied to each variable. Interrogate flag variable attributes `flag_masks` and `flag_meanings` to find the flags for each variable.

- `roll_exceeds_threshold` - No flag description provided.

3.13 GeneralEastern

`p_general_eastern.py`

Processing module to calculate Dew Point temperature from the General Eastern 1011B chilled mirror hygrometer. Counts from the core console are converted to dew point with a polynomial fit, using coefficients provided in the flight constants parameter `CALGE`. The General Eastern provides a control signal voltage to indicate whether the instrument is controlling on a dew point, and the data are flagged when outside this range. The valid range is provided through the flight constants parameter `GELIMS`.

3.13.1 Outputs

- **TDEW_GE**
 - `_FillValue`: -9999
 - `actual_range`: [`<float32: derived_from_file>`, `<float32: derived_from_file>`]
 - `ancillary_variables`: `TDEW_GE_FLAG`
 - `calibration_information`: This instrument cannot be calibrated
 - `coordinates`: `<str: derived_from_file optional>`
 - `coverage_content_type`: `physicalMeasurement`
 - `frequency`: 4
 - `instrument_manufacturer`: General Eastern Instruments
 - `instrument_model`: 1011B Chilled Mirror Hygrometer
 - `instrument_serial_number`: `<str: derived_from_file>`
 - `long_name`: Dew Point from the General Eastern instrument
 - `standard_name`: `dew_point_temperature`
 - `units`: `degK`

3.13.2 Flags

Variables in this module use bitmask flags. Some, all or none of these flags may be applied to each variable. Interrogate flag variable attributes `flag_masks` and `flag_meanings` to find the flags for each variable.

- `control_data_missing` - No control data is available. The instrument may or may not be controlling on a dew point
- `control_out_of_range` - The control signal is outside of the specified valid range [7000, 5000]
- `dewpoint_out_of_range` - Dew point outside valid range [195, 394] K

3.14 Gin

`p_gin.py`

This module provides variables from the Applanix POS AV 410 GPS-aided inertial navigation system (GIN). The GIN provides parameters at a frequency of 50 Hz; this module simply downsamples these parameters to 32 Hz.

The `STATUS_GIN` parameter gives the current solution status reported by the GIN. This is defined as

- 0: Full Nav. (user accuracies met)
- 1: Fine Align (heading RMS < 15 deg)
- 2: GC CHI 2 (alignment w/ GPS, RMS heading error > 15 deg)
- 3: PC CHI 2 (alignment w/o GPS, RMS heading error > 15 deg)
- 4: GC GHI 1 (alignment w/ GPS, RMS heading error > 45 deg)
- 5: PC CHI 1 (alignment w/o GPS, RMS heading error > 45 deg)
- 6: Course levelling active
- 7: Initial solution assigned
- 8: No solution

3.14.1 Outputs

- **LAT_GIN**
 - `_FillValue`: -9999
 - `actual_range`: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - `ancillary_variables`: LAT_GIN_FLAG
 - `coordinates`: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - `coverage_content_type`: physicalMeasurement
 - `frequency`: 32
 - `instrument_manufacturer`: Applanix
 - `instrument_model`: POS AV 410
 - `long_name`: Latitude from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit
 - `standard_name`: latitude
 - `units`: degree_north
- **LON_GIN**
 - `_FillValue`: -9999

- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: LON_GIN_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32
- instrument_manufacturer: Applanix
- instrument_model: POS AV 410
- long_name: Longitude from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit
- standard_name: longitude
- units: degree_east

- **ALT_GIN**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: ALT_GIN_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32
- instrument_manufacturer: Applanix
- instrument_model: POS AV 410
- long_name: Altitude from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit
- standard_name: altitude
- units: m

- **VELN_GIN**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: VELN_GIN_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32
- instrument_manufacturer: Applanix
- instrument_model: POS AV 410
- long_name: Aircraft velocity north from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit
- units: m s-l

- **VELE_GIN**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: VELE_GIN_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement

- frequency: 32
- instrument_manufacturer: Applanix
- instrument_model: POS AV 410
- long_name: Aircraft velocity east from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit
- units: m s-1

- **VELD_GIN**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: VELD_GIN_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32
- instrument_manufacturer: Applanix
- instrument_model: POS AV 410
- long_name: Aircraft velocity down from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit
- units: m s-1

- **ROLL_GIN**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: ROLL_GIN_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32
- instrument_manufacturer: Applanix
- instrument_model: POS AV 410
- long_name: Roll angle from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit
- standard_name: platform_roll_angle
- units: degree

- **PTCH_GIN**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: PTCH_GIN_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32
- instrument_manufacturer: Applanix
- instrument_model: POS AV 410
- long_name: Pitch angle from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit
- standard_name: platform_pitch_angle

- units: degree
- **HDG_GIN**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: HDG_GIN_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 32
 - instrument_manufacturer: Applanix
 - instrument_model: POS AV 410
 - long_name: Heading from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit
 - standard_name: platform_yaw_angle
 - units: degree
- **WAND_GIN**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: WAND_GIN_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 32
 - instrument_manufacturer: Applanix
 - instrument_model: POS AV 410
 - long_name: Wander angle from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit
 - units: degree s-1
- **TRCK_GIN**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: TRCK_GIN_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 32
 - instrument_manufacturer: Applanix
 - instrument_model: POS AV 410
 - long_name: Aircraft track angle from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit
 - standard_name: platform_course
 - units: degree
- **GSPD_GIN**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']

- ancillary_variables: GSPD_GIN_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32
- instrument_manufacturer: Applanix
- instrument_model: POS AV 410
- long_name: Groundspeed from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit
- standard_name: platform_speed_wrt_ground
- units: m s-1

- **ROLR_GIN**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: ROLR_GIN_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32
- instrument_manufacturer: Applanix
- instrument_model: POS AV 410
- long_name: Rate-of-change of roll angle from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit
- standard_name: platform_roll_rate
- units: degree s-1

- **PITR_GIN**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: PITR_GIN_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32
- instrument_manufacturer: Applanix
- instrument_model: POS AV 410
- long_name: Rate-of-change of pitch angle from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit
- standard_name: platform_pitch_rate
- units: degree s-1

- **HDGR_GIN**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: HDGR_GIN_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement

- frequency: 32
- instrument_manufacturer: Applanix
- instrument_model: POS AV 410
- long_name: Rate-of-change of heading from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit
- standard_name: platform_yaw_rate
- units: degree s-1
- **ACLF_GIN**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: ACLF_GIN_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 32
 - instrument_manufacturer: Applanix
 - instrument_model: POS AV 410
 - long_name: Acceleration along the aircraft longitudinal axis from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit (positive forward)
 - units: m s-2
- **ACLS_GIN**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: ACLS_GIN_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 32
 - instrument_manufacturer: Applanix
 - instrument_model: POS AV 410
 - long_name: Acceleration along the aircraft transverse axis from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit (positive starboard)
 - units: m s-2
- **ACLD_GIN**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: ACLD_GIN_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 32
 - instrument_manufacturer: Applanix
 - instrument_model: POS AV 410

- long_name: Acceleration along the aircraft vertical axis from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit (positive down)
- units: m s⁻²
- **STATUS_GIN**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: STATUS_GIN_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 32
 - instrument_manufacturer: Applanix
 - instrument_model: POS AV 410
 - long_name: Solution status from POS AV 410 GPS-aided Inertial Navigation unit
 - units: 1

3.14.2 Flags

Variables in this module use bitmask flags. Some, all or none of these flags may be applied to each variable. Interrogate flag variable attributes `flag_masks` and `flag_meanings` to find the flags for each variable.

- `no_solution` - The GIN status flag indicates no solution has been obtained.
- `latlon_identically_zero` - Latitude and Longitude are exactly zero. This indicates an erroneous data message.

3.15 Heimann

`p_heimann.py`

Processing for the Heimann Radiometer. The Heimann outputs a voltage with a range of 0 - 10 V corresponding to an inferred brightness temperature of -50 - 50 °C. This module simply applies a linear transformation to the counts recorded on the DLU to convert counts → volts → temperature. During a calibration, temperature from the black body are reported. Parameters for the linear transformations are taken from the flight constant parameters `HEIMCAL` for the Heimann and `PRTCCAL` for the PRT on the black body.

3.15.1 Outputs

- **BTHEIM_U**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: BTHEIM_U_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 4
 - instrument_manufacturer: Heitronics
 - instrument_model: KT19.82

- instrument_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
- long_name: Uncorrected brightness temperature from the Heimann radiometer
- units: K

3.15.2 Flags

Variables in this module use bitmask flags. Some, all or none of these flags may be applied to each variable. Interrogate flag variable attributes `flag_masks` and `flag_meanings` to find the flags for each variable.

- `aircraft_on_ground` - The aircraft is on the ground
- `data_out_of_range` - Brightness temperature is outside the range 253.15 - 313.15 K
- `in_calibration` - The Heimann is in a calibration cycle. Black body temperature is being reported
- `data_missing` - Data are expected but not present

3.16 KippZonenPyrgeometer

`p_pyrgeometer.py`

Calculation of longwave fluxes from the upward and downward facing Kipp and Zonen CR4 Pyrgeometers.

The 0 - 32 mV output of the CR4 thermopile is mapped to a 4 - 20 mA signal in the amp box, which carries sensor specific calibrations, corresponding to a flux range of $-600 - 200 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$. This is then converted to a voltage using a 350Ω resistor, which is recorded in the DLU, with 16 bits covering a $-10 - 10 \text{ V}$ range. Similarly, the thermistor is placed in parallel with a $100 \text{ k}\Omega$ linearising resistor, and $100 \mu\text{A}$ is passed through the combination, with the resulting voltage measured at the DLU.

This module first applies the inverse transformations to recover the amp box current and the thermistor resistance. The thermistor temperature is given by

$$T = \left(\alpha + \left(\beta \log(R) + \gamma \log(R)^3 \right) \right)^{-1},$$

where R is the thermistor resistance and α , β , and γ are calibration coefficients supplied by the manufacturer. The longwave flux, L_D , is then given by

$$L_D = \beta(A - \alpha) - \gamma + \sigma T^4,$$

where $\alpha = 4$, $\beta = 50$, and $\gamma = 600$ map the current from the amp box, A , onto the specified range of flux values, T is the temperature recorded by the thermistor, and σ is the Stefan-Boltzmann constant.

3.16.1 Outputs

- `IR_UP_C`
 - `_FillValue`: -9999
 - `actual_range`: [`<float32: derived_from_file>`, `<float32: derived_from_file>`]
 - `ancillary_variables`: `IR_UP_C_FLAG`
 - `coordinates`: `<str: derived_from_file optional>`
 - `coverage_content_type`: `physicalMeasurement`
 - `frequency`: 1
 - `instrument_manufacturer`: Kipp and Zonen
 - `instrument_model`: CGR 4

- instrument_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
- long_name: Corrected upward longwave irradiance
- units: W m-2
- **IR_DN_C**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: IR_DN_C_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 1
 - instrument_manufacturer: Kipp and Zonen
 - instrument_model: CGR 4
 - instrument_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
 - long_name: Corrected downward longwave irradiance
 - units: W m-2

3.16.2 Flags

Variables in this module use bitmask flags. Some, all or none of these flags may be applied to each variable. Interrogate flag variable attributes `flag_masks` and `flag_meanings` to find the flags for each variable.

- `aircraft_on_ground` - Aircraft is on the ground

3.17 Nephelometer

`p_nephelometer.py`

Provides data and flagging information from the TSI nephelometer. The data from the nephelometer do not require any further processing, however this module parses the instrument status information to provide a QC flag for the data.

Note

Prior to software version 24.0.0, this module used classic flagging. From version 24.0.0, the module uses bitmask flagging, and further flagging may be added by standalone flagging modules.

3.17.1 Outputs

- **TSC_BLUU**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: TSC_BLUU_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement

- frequency: 1
- instrument_manufacturer: TSI
- instrument_model: 3563
- long_name: Uncorrected blue total scattering coefficient from TSI 3563 Nephelometer
- units: m-1
- **TSC_GRNU**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: TSC_GRNU_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 1
 - instrument_manufacturer: TSI
 - instrument_model: 3563
 - long_name: Uncorrected green total scattering coefficient from TSI 3563 Nephelometer
 - units: m-1
- **TSC_REDU**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: TSC_REDU_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 1
 - instrument_manufacturer: TSI
 - instrument_model: 3563
 - long_name: Uncorrected red total scattering coefficient from TSI 3563 Nephelometer
 - units: m-1
- **BSC_BLUU**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: BSC_BLUU_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 1
 - instrument_manufacturer: TSI
 - instrument_model: 3563
 - long_name: Uncorrected blue back scattering coefficient from TSI 3563 Nephelometer
 - units: m-1
- **BSC_GRNU**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: BSC_GRNU_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 1
- instrument_manufacturer: TSI
- instrument_model: 3563
- long_name: Uncorrected green back scattering coefficient from TSI 3563 Nephelometer
- units: m-1

- **BSC_REDU**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: BSC_REDU_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 1
- instrument_manufacturer: TSI
- instrument_model: 3563
- long_name: Uncorrected red back scattering coefficient from TSI 3563 Nephelometer
- units: m-1

- **NEPH_PR**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: NEPH_PR_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 1
- instrument_manufacturer: TSI
- instrument_model: 3563
- long_name: Internal sample pressure of the Nephelometer
- units: hPa

- **NEPH_T**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: NEPH_T_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 1

- instrument_manufacturer: TSI
- instrument_model: 3563
- long_name: Internal sample temperature of the Nephelometer
- units: K
- **NEPH_RH**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: NEPH_RH_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 1
 - instrument_manufacturer: TSI
 - instrument_model: 3563
 - long_name: Relative humidity from TSI 3563 Nephelometer
 - units: %

3.17.2 Flags

Variables in this module use bitmask flags. Some, all or none of these flags may be applied to each variable. Interrogate flag variable attributes `flag_masks` and `flag_meanings` to find the flags for each variable.

- `instrument_flag_raised` - A fault has been raised by the instrument

3.18 Nevzorov

`p_nevzorov.py`

Post processing for liquid and total water from the Nevzorov Vane. Works with both 1T1L2R and 1T2L1R vanes, which should be specified in the flight constants as `VANETYPE`.

The Nevzorov hot-wire probe measures total and liquid water content by recording the powers required to hold exposed and sheltered wires at a constant temperature.

The water content, W , measured by a collector is given by

$$W = \frac{P_c - K P_r}{V_t A L},$$

where P_c is the collector power, P_r is the reference power, K is the baseline, the ratio of P_c and P_r in clear air, V_t is the true air speed, A is the forward-facing area of the collector, and L is the energy required to melt and then evaporate the water impacted on the sensor, specified in the flight constants as `CALNVL`.

The baseline, K , is not a true constant, but varies with the ambient conditions. [Abel et al. \(2014\)](#) parameterise K as a function of indicated air speed, V_{IAS} and ambient pressure, P ,

$$K = \alpha_{IAS} \frac{1}{V_{IAS}} + \alpha_P \log_{10}(P).$$

If, for any reason, the fitting above fails, then only the uncorrected outputs, using a constant K specified in the flight constants, are written to file.

The outputs listed produced by this module depend on the type of Nevzorov vane fitted to the aircraft. If an old-style 1T1L2R vane is fitted, then the default outputs are `NV_TWC_C`, `NV_LWC_C`,

NV_TWC_COL_P, NV_LWC_COL_P, NV_TWC_REF_P, NV_LWC_REF_P. If a new-style `1T2L1R` vane is fitted, then the default outputs are *NV_TWC_C, NV_LWC1_C, NV_LWC2_C, NV_TWC_COL_P, NV_LWC1_COL_P, NV_LWC2_COL_P, NV_REF_P*.

Note

Prior to software version ?? this module output uncorrected water content data (*NV_TWC_U, NV_LWC_U, NV_LWC1_U, NV_LWC2_U*), instead of the element powers. These outputs are no longer produced.

3.18.1 Outputs

- **NV_TWC_C**

- `_FillValue`: -9999
- `actual_range`: [`<float32: derived_from_file>`, `<float32: derived_from_file>`]
- `ancillary_variables`: NV_TWC_C_FLAG
- `comment`: Automatically baselined using flight data.
- `coordinates`: `<str: derived_from_file optional>`
- `coverage_content_type`: physicalMeasurement
- `frequency`: 64
- `instrument_manufacturer`: Sky Phys Tech Inc.
- `instrument_model`: `<str: derived_from_file>`
- `instrument_serial_number`: `<str: derived_from_file>`
- `long_name`: Corrected total condensed water content from the Nevzorov probe
- `units`: gram m-3

- **NV_TWC_COL_P**

- `_FillValue`: -9999
- `actual_range`: [`<float32: derived_from_file>`, `<float32: derived_from_file>`]
- `ancillary_variables`: NV_TWC_COL_P_FLAG
- `coordinates`: `<str: derived_from_file optional>`
- `coverage_content_type`: physicalMeasurement
- `frequency`: 64
- `instrument_manufacturer`: Sky Phys Tech Inc.
- `instrument_model`: `<str: derived_from_file>`
- `instrument_serial_number`: `<str: derived_from_file>`
- `long_name`: TWC collector power
- `units`: W

- **NV_TWC_REF_P**

- `_FillValue`: -9999
- `actual_range`: [`<float32: derived_from_file>`, `<float32: derived_from_file>`]
- `ancillary_variables`: NV_TWC_REF_P_FLAG
- `coordinates`: `<str: derived_from_file optional>`

- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 64
 - instrument_manufacturer: Sky Phys Tech Inc.
 - instrument_model: <str: derived_from_file>
 - instrument_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
 - long_name: TWC reference power
 - units: W
- **NV_REF_P**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: NV_REF_P_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 64
 - instrument_manufacturer: Sky Phys Tech Inc.
 - instrument_model: <str: derived_from_file>
 - instrument_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
 - long_name: Reference power
 - units: W
- **NV_LWC_C**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: NV_LWC_C_FLAG
 - comment: Automatically baselined using flight data.
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 64
 - instrument_manufacturer: Sky Phys Tech Inc.
 - instrument_model: <str: derived_from_file>
 - instrument_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
 - long_name: Corrected liquid water content from the Nevzorov probe
 - standard_name: mass_concentration_of_liquid_water_in_air
 - units: gram m-3
- **NV_LWC_COL_P**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: NV_LWC_COL_P_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement

- frequency: 64
 - instrument_manufacturer: Sky Phys Tech Inc.
 - instrument_model: <str: derived_from_file>
 - instrument_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
 - long_name: LWC collector power
 - units: W
- **NV_LWC_REF_P**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: NV_LWC_REF_P_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 64
 - instrument_manufacturer: Sky Phys Tech Inc.
 - instrument_model: <str: derived_from_file>
 - instrument_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
 - long_name: LWC reference power
 - units: W
- **NV_LWC1_C**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: NV_LWC1_C_FLAG
 - comment: Automatically baselined using flight data.
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 64
 - instrument_manufacturer: Sky Phys Tech Inc.
 - instrument_model: <str: derived_from_file>
 - instrument_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
 - long_name: Corrected liquid water content from the Nevzorov probe (1st collector)
 - standard_name: mass_concentration_of_liquid_water_in_air
 - units: gram m-3
- **NV_LWC1_COL_P**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: NV_LWC1_COL_P_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 64

- instrument_manufacturer: Sky Phys Tech Inc.
 - instrument_model: <str: derived_from_file>
 - instrument_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
 - long_name: LWC1 collector power
 - units: W
- **NV_LWC2_C**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: NV_LWC2_C_FLAG
 - comment: Automatically baselined using flight data.
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 64
 - instrument_manufacturer: Sky Phys Tech Inc.
 - instrument_model: <str: derived_from_file>
 - instrument_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
 - long_name: Corrected liquid water content from the Nevzorov probe (2nd collector)
 - standard_name: mass_concentration_of_liquid_water_in_air
 - units: gram m-3
- **NV_LWC2_COL_P**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: NV_LWC2_COL_P_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 64
 - instrument_manufacturer: Sky Phys Tech Inc.
 - instrument_model: <str: derived_from_file>
 - instrument_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
 - long_name: LWC2 collector power
 - units: W
- **NV_CLEAR_AIR_MASK**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: NV_CLEAR_AIR_MASK_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 64
 - instrument_manufacturer: Sky Phys Tech Inc.

- instrument_model: <str: derived_from_file>
- instrument_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
- long_name: Clear air mask based on Nevzorov Total Water power variance
- units: None

3.18.2 Flags

Variables in this module use bitmask flags. Some, all or none of these flags may be applied to each variable. Interrogate flag variable attributes `flag_masks` and `flag_meanings` to find the flags for each variable.

- aircraft_on_ground - The aircraft is on the ground
- poor_clear_air_baseline - The Nevzorov baseline correction is poor in clear air ($|dk| > 0.02$)

3.19 PRTTemperatureUncertainties

`p_prt_uncertainties.py`

For further details see the [FAAM Met. Handbook](#).

This module calculates combined uncertainty estimates for indicated and true air temperatures, when these are recorded with platinum resistance thermometers.

Uncertainties in the indicated temperatures are derived from:

- Uncertainty in the thermometer calibration from NPL
- Drift of sensors between NPL calibrations
- Resolution uncertainty in the DECADES DLU
- DECADES calibration uncertainty
- Noise in the system when a fixed resistor is fitted
- Keithley calibration
- Keithley stability
- DECADES calibration (counts to resistance) residual
- NPL calibration (resistance to temperature) residual.

Uncertainties in the true air temperatures are derived from:

- Uncertainty of the corresponding indicated air temperature
- Uncertainty in the Mach number
- Uncertainty in the ratio of specific heats
- Uncertainty in the variable housing recovery factor.

3.19.1 Outputs

- **IAT_ND_R_CU**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: IAT_ND_R_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: auxiliaryInformation
 - frequency: 32
 - long_name: Combined uncertainty estimate for IAT_ND_R
 - units: K
- **TAT_ND_R_CU**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: TAT_ND_R_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: auxiliaryInformation
 - frequency: 32
 - long_name: Combined uncertainty estimate for TAT_ND_R
 - units: K
- **IAT_DI_R_CU**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: IAT_DI_R_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: auxiliaryInformation
 - frequency: 32
 - long_name: Combined uncertainty estimate for IAT_DI_R
 - units: K
- **TAT_DI_R_CU**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: TAT_DI_R_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: auxiliaryInformation
 - frequency: 32
 - long_name: Combined uncertainty estimate for TAT_DI_R
 - units: K

3.19.2 Flags

3.20 PRTTemperatures

p_prt_temps.py

For further details see the [FAAM Met. Handbook](#).

Calculate indicated and true (static) air temperatures from the deiced and non-deiced Rosemount housings, when fitted with platinum resistance thermometer sensors. Indicated temperatures are calculated with a polynomial transformation of the DLU signal, using calibration factors in constants variables CALDIT and CALNDT, which incorporates the DLU and sensor calibrations.

The deiced indicated temperature is subject to a heating correction term when the heater is active, given by

$$\Delta T_{\text{IAT}} = \frac{1}{10} \exp(\exp(a + (\log(M) + b)(c(q + P) + d))),$$

where M is the Mach number, q is the dynamic pressure and P the static pressure. The parameters a , b , c , and d are

$$[1.171, 2.738, -0.000568, -0.452].$$

True air temperatures are a function of indicated temperatures, Mach number and housing recovery factor, and are given by

$$T_{\text{TAT}} = \frac{T_{\text{IAT}}}{1 + (0.2R_f M^2)},$$

where M is the Mach number and R_f the recovery factor. Recovery factors are calculated in the processing module *RecoveryFactor*.

A flag is applied to the data when the Mach number is out of range. **Further flags may be added by standalone flagging modules.**

3.20.1 Outputs

- TAT_ND_R

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: TAT_ND_R_FLAG
- calibration_date: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- calibration_information: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- calibration_url: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- comment: Sensor housed in Rosemount Aerospace Inc. Type 102 non-deiced Total Temperature Housing
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32
- long_name: True air temperature from the Rosemount non-deiced temperature sensor
- sensor_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
- sensor_type: <str: derived_from_file>
- standard_name: air_temperature

- units: K
- **TAT_DI_R**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: TAT_DI_R_FLAG
 - calibration_date: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - calibration_information: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - calibration_url: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - comment: Sensor housed in Rosemount Aerospace Inc. Type 102 deiced Total Temperature Housing
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 32
 - long_name: True air temperature from the Rosemount deiced temperature sensor
 - sensor_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
 - sensor_type: <str: derived_from_file>
 - standard_name: air_temperature
 - units: K
- **IAT_ND_R**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: IAT_ND_R_FLAG
 - calibration_date: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - calibration_information: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - calibration_url: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - comment: Sensor housed in Rosemount Aerospace Inc. Type 102 non-deiced Total Temperature Housing
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 32
 - long_name: Indicated air temperature from the Rosemount non-deiced temperature sensor
 - sensor_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
 - sensor_type: <str: derived_from_file>
 - units: K
- **IAT_DI_R**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: IAT_DI_R_FLAG
 - calibration_date: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - calibration_information: <str: derived_from_file optional>

- calibration_url: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- comment: Sensor housed in Rosemount Aerospace Inc. Type 102 deiced Total Temperature Housing
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32
- long_name: Indicated air temperature from the Rosemount deiced temperature sensor
- sensor_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
- sensor_type: <str: derived_from_file>
- units: K

3.20.2 Flags

Variables in this module use bitmask flags. Some, all or none of these flags may be applied to each variable. Interrogate flag variable attributes `flag_masks` and `flag_meanings` to find the flags for each variable.

- mach_out_of_range - Mach number is below acceptable minimum of 0.05

3.21 PSAP

`p_psap.py`

Reports data from the Radiance Research Particle Soot Absorbition Photometer. The following transformations are applied to the data from the aerosol rack DLU:

$$F = \frac{F_{\text{DLU}}}{2},$$

$$P_{\text{lin}} = \frac{P_{\text{linDLU}}}{2 \times 10^5},$$

$$P_{\text{log}} = 10^{(P_{\text{logDLU}}/2)-7},$$

$$T = \frac{T_{\text{DLU}}}{8},$$

where P_{lin} , P_{log} , F , and T correspond to the outputs PSAP_LIN, PSAP_LOG, PSAP_FLO, and PSAP_TRA respectively. Flagging is based on the flow rate and transmittance ratio limits.

3.21.1 Outputs

- PSAP_FLO
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: [<float32: derived_from_file>, <float32: derived_from_file>]
 - ancillary_variables: PSAP_FLO_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 1
 - instrument_manufacturer: Radiance Research
 - long_name: PSAP Flow

- units: l min-1

• **PSAP_LIN**

- _FillValue: -9999

- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']

- ancillary_variables: PSAP_LIN_FLAG

- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>

- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement

- frequency: 1

- instrument_manufacturer: Radiance Research

- long_name: Uncorrected absorption coefficient at 565nm, linear, from PSAP

- units: m-1

• **PSAP_LOG**

- _FillValue: -9999

- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']

- ancillary_variables: PSAP_LOG_FLAG

- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>

- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement

- frequency: 1

- instrument_manufacturer: Radiance Research

- long_name: Uncorrected absorption coefficient at 565nm, log, from PSAP

- units: 1

• **PSAP_TRA**

- _FillValue: -9999

- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']

- ancillary_variables: PSAP_TRA_FLAG

- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>

- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement

- frequency: 1

- instrument_manufacturer: Radiance Research

- long_name: PSAP Transmittance

- units: percent

3.21.2 Flags

Variables in this module use bitmask flags. Some, all or none of these flags may be applied to each variable. Interrogate flag variable attributes `flag_masks` and `flag_meanings` to find the flags for each variable.

- `transmittance_out_of_range` - Transmittance ratio is outside the valid range [0.5, 1.05]
- `flow_out_of_range` - PSAP flow is out of range. This most likely indicates that the PSAP interrupt is active, to prevent water ingress

3.22 RadAlt

`p_radalt.py`

Calculate the radar altitude, in metres. The radar altitude, from `radalt2`, is read from the aircraft ARINC-429 data bus at the rear core console, and recoded at a frequency of 2 Hz. The signal is received as a 16 bit signed integer, with a least significant bit resolution of 0.25 ft, giving a max valid value of $((2^{16}/2) - 1)/4$.

Data are flagged when below 10 feet or above 5000 feet, which is the nominal maximum range of the instrument, though altitude is reported up to 8000 ft.

3.22.1 Outputs

- **HGT_RADR**
 - `_FillValue`: -9999
 - `actual_range`: [`<float32: derived_from_file>`, `<float32: derived_from_file>`]
 - `ancillary_variables`: HGT_RADR_FLAG
 - `coordinates`: `<str: derived_from_file optional>`
 - `coverage_content_type`: `physicalMeasurement`
 - `frequency`: 2
 - `instrument_manufacturer`: Thales
 - `instrument_model`: AVH16 Radar Altimeter
 - `long_name`: Radar height from the aircraft radar altimeter
 - `standard_name`: height
 - `units`: m

3.22.2 Flags

Variables in this module use bitmask flags. Some, all or none of these flags may be applied to each variable. Interrogate flag variable attributes `flag_masks` and `flag_meanings` to find the flags for each variable.

- `data_out_of_range` - RadAlt reading outside valid range (10.00, 1524.00)
- `aircraft_on_ground` - The aircraft is on the ground, as indicated by the weight on wheels flag.

3.23 RecoveryFactor

p_recovery_factor.py

For further details see the [FAAM Met. Handbook](#).

This module produces a Mach dependent recovery factor for the deiced and non-deiced Rosemount housings, which house the temperature probes.

The recovery factor for the non-deiced housing is given by Rosemount Aerospace as

$$\eta_{nd} = a_1 M + a_2 M^2$$

where $a_1 = 0.0014054157$ and $a_2 = -0.00060943146$

The recovery factor for the deiced housing is calculated from in-flight data, under the assumption that the recovery factor given by Rosemount is correct. It is given by

$$\eta_{di} = 1 - \alpha (1 - \eta_{nd}),$$

where $\alpha = 0.9989$ is the average ratio of deiced and non-deiced indicated temperatures. Further information is available in the FAAM Recovery Factor report (H. Price, document # FAAM013006).

Uncertainties are given by

$$\begin{aligned}\alpha_U &= 0.0006 \\ \eta_{nd,U} &= -0.0003458119M^2 + 0.00059345748M \\ \eta_{di,U} &= ((\eta_{nd} - 1)^2 \alpha_U^2 + \alpha^2 \eta_{nd,U}^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}\end{aligned}$$

3.23.1 Outputs

- **ETA_ND**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32
- long_name: Variable recovery factor for non-deiced Rosemount housing
- units: 1

- **ETA_DI**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32
- long_name: Variable recovery factor for deiced Rosemount housing
- units: 1

- **ETA_ND_CU**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']

- ancillary_variables: ETA_ND_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: auxiliaryInformation
 - frequency: 32
 - long_name: Uncertainty in recovery factor for deiced Rosemount housing
 - units: 1
- **ETA_DI_CU**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: ETA_DI_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: auxiliaryInformation
 - frequency: 32
 - long_name: Uncertainty in recovery factor for non-deiced Rosemount housing
 - units: 1

3.23.2 Flags

3.24 Rvsm

p_rvsm.py

Calculate derived parameters from the aircraft's RVSM system. Pressure altitude and indicated air speed are obtained from the aircraft's ARINC-429 data bus, with a least significant bit resolution of 4 ft and 1/32 kts respectively.

Static pressure, P , is obtained from the pressure altitude, Z_p , using the ICAO standard atmosphere,

$$P = P_0 \left(\frac{T_0}{T_0 + L_0 (Z_p - h_0)} \right)^{\frac{g_0 M}{R L_0}},$$

where $T_0 = 288.15$, $L_0 = -0.0065$, $h_0 = 0$, $g_0 = 9.80655$, $M = 0.0289644$, $R = 8.31432$, $P_0 = 1013.25$ below 11000 m, or

$$P = P_1 \exp \left(\frac{-g_0 M (Z_p - h_1)}{R T_1} \right),$$

where $T_1 = 216.65$, $P_1 = 226.321$, $h_1 = 11000$, above 11000 m.

Pitot static pressure, q , is given as

$$q = P \left(\frac{M^2}{5} + 1 \right)^{\frac{7}{2}} - 1,$$

with the Mach number, M , given by

$$M = \frac{V_{IAS}}{V_0 \sqrt{\frac{P}{P_0}}},$$

where $V_0 = 340.294$ and $P_0 = 1013.25$, and V_{IAS} is the indicated air speed.

Data are flagged where either the pressure altitude or indicated air speed are considered out of range.

3.24.1 Outputs

- **PS_RVSM**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: PS_RVSM_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32
- instrument_manufacturer: BAE Systems
- long_name: Static pressure from the aircraft RVSM (air data) system
- standard_name: air_pressure
- units: hPa

- **PALT_RVS**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: PALT_RVS_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32
- instrument_manufacturer: BAE Systems
- long_name: Pressure altitude from the aircraft RVSM (air data) system
- standard_name: barometric_altitude
- units: m

- **Q_RVSM**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: Q_RVSM_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32
- instrument_manufacturer: BAE Systems
- long_name: Pitot static pressure inverted from RVSM (air data) system indicated airspeed
- units: hPa

3.24.2 Flags

Variables in this module use bitmask flags. Some, all or none of these flags may be applied to each variable. Interrogate flag variable attributes `flag_masks` and `flag_meanings` to find the flags for each variable.

- `instrument_not_ready` - The RVSM system may not be ready for use
- `altitude_out_of_range` - Pressure altitude outside acceptable range [-2000, 50000]
- `ias_out_of_range` - Indicated air speed outside acceptable range [-50, 500]

3.25 S10Pressure

`p_s10_pressure.py`

Calculate static pressure from the S10 fuselage ports. Static pressure is calculated by applying a polynomial transformation to the DLU signal. The coefficients, specified in the flight constants parameter `CALS10SP`, combine both the DLU and pressure transducer calibrations.

Data are flagged when they are considered out of range.

3.25.1 Outputs

- **P10_STAT**
 - `_FillValue`: -9999
 - `actual_range`: [`<float32: derived_from_file>`, `<float32: derived_from_file>`]
 - `ancillary_variables`: `P10_STAT_FLAG`
 - `coordinates`: `<str: derived_from_file optional>`
 - `coverage_content_type`: `physicalMeasurement`
 - `frequency`: 32
 - `long_name`: Static pressure from S10 fuselage ports
 - `sensor_manufacturer`: Rosemount Aerospace Inc.
 - `sensor_model`: 1201F2
 - `sensor_serial_number`: `<str: derived_from_file>`
 - `standard_name`: `air_pressure`
 - `units`: hPa

3.25.2 Flags

Variables in this module use bitmask flags. Some, all or none of these flags may be applied to each variable. Interrogate flag variable attributes `flag_masks` and `flag_meanings` to find the flags for each variable.

- `data_out_of_range` - Pressure outside acceptable limits [100, 1050]

3.26 S9Pressure

p_s9_pressure.py

Calculate static pressure from the S9 fuselage ports. Static pressure is calculated by applying a polynomial transformation to the DLU signal. The coefficients, specified in the flight constants parameter CALS9SP, combine both the DLU and pressure transducer calibrations. Additionally, a Mach dependent ‘position error’ correction term is applied, aimed at accounting for the unknown position error associated with the S9 port, derived by minimising errors between the S9 and RVSM static pressure measurements. This correction is of the form

$$\Delta P = \alpha M^\beta,$$

with parameters α and β specified in the flight constants parameter S9_PE_C.

Data are flagged when they are considered out of range.

3.26.1 Outputs

- **P9_STAT**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: P9_STAT_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32
- long_name: Static pressure from S9 fuselage ports
- sensor_manufacturer: Rosemount Aerospace Inc.
- sensor_model: 1201F2
- sensor_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
- standard_name: air_pressure
- units: hPa

- **P9_STAT_U**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: P9_STAT_U_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32
- long_name: Static pressure from S9 fuselage ports, uncorrected
- sensor_manufacturer: Rosemount Aerospace Inc.
- sensor_model: 1201F2
- sensor_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
- standard_name: air_pressure
- units: hPa

3.26.2 Flags

Variables in this module use bitmask flags. Some, all or none of these flags may be applied to each variable. Interrogate flag variable attributes `flag_masks` and `flag_meanings` to find the flags for each variable.

- `data_out_of_range` - Pressure outside acceptable limits [100, 1050]

3.27 SeaProbe

`p_seaprobe.py`

Calculates bulk water contents from the SEA WCM-2000 sensor.

Element Power

First element powers $P = V * I$ are derived from recorded voltages and currents for each element (TWC, 083, 021, CMP, DCE).

Cloud mask

A cloud mask is derived using a rolling window applied to the TWC element temperature, with the aircraft assumed to be in cloud whenever the temperature range within the rolling window exceeds a specified range, or where the temperature within the window exceeds a specified high or low value.

Parameters

Temperature of evaporation, T_{evap} , and latent heat of evaporation, L_{evap} , are given by

$$\begin{aligned} T_{\text{evap}} &= 32.16 + 0.1901P - 2.391 \times 10^{-4}P^2 + 1.785 \times 10^{-7}P^3 - 5.19 \times 10^4, \\ L_{\text{evap}} &= 4.1868 (594.4 - 0.484T_{\text{evap}} - 7 \times 10^{-4}T_{\text{evap}}^2), \end{aligned}$$

where P is the static pressure from the aircraft's air data system.

The specific energies for evaporation and sublimation, L_{liq} and L_{ice} , are given by

$$L_{\text{liq}} = C_{\text{liq}}(T_{\text{evap}} - T_a) + L_{\text{evap}},$$

where T_a is the ambient air temperature, and

$$C_{\text{liq}}(T) = 4.169828 + (0.000364(T + 100)^{5.26}) \cdot 10^{-10} + 0.046709 \cdot 10^{-0.036T},$$

and

$$L_{\text{ice}} = C_{\text{ice}}(T) + L_{\text{ice}} + C_{\text{liq}}(T_{\text{evap}}) + L_{\text{evap}},$$

where $L_{\text{ice}} = 333.5$, and C_{ice} is given by an interpolant between $T = [77, 173, 273]$ and $C = [0.686, 1.372, 2.097]$.

Dry air term

The dry air compensation term is calculated in two methods, with the method which gives the best fit being used

- Method 1: Calculate dry air power term by fitting constants for 1st principles.

The calculation of the dry air power term is based on method three as described on page 58 of the WCM-2000 manual. This uses a fit between the theoretical and measured (in cloud-free conditions) sense powers to find the fitting constants k_1 and k_2 ($k_2 \approx 0.5$).

$$\begin{aligned} P_{\text{sense,dry}} &= k_1(T - T_a)(P \times \text{TAS})^{k_2} \\ P_{\text{sense,total}} &= P_{\text{sense,dry}} + P_{\text{sense,wet}} \\ &\rightarrow P_{\text{sense,total}} - P_{\text{sense,dry}} = 0 \text{ in cloud-free conditions.} \end{aligned}$$

- Method 2: Calculate dry air power term from compensation element measurements.

The calculation of the dry air power term (DAT) is based on the use of the compensation element as described on page 56 of the WCM-2000 manual. This finds the slope and offset for conversion of the compensation power to dry air sense element power.

$$P_{\text{sense,dry}} = P_0 + KP_{\text{comp}}$$

$$P_{\text{sense,total}} = P_0 + KP_{\text{comp}} \text{ when in clear air}$$

This will be TAS and P dependent (possibly T_a). This function determines optimum fitting parameters for the entire dataset, thus any baseline drift shall be lost.

Sense element water content

The water content for an element is given by

$$W = \frac{(2.389 \times 10^5)P_{\text{sense}}}{L_{\text{evap}} + (T_{\text{evap}} - T_a) \times \text{TAS} \times w \times h}$$

where P_{sense} is the (wet) sense element power, and w and h are the width and height of the sense element, respectively.

Note

The flags on upstream variables TAT_DI_R and TAS_RVSM are not included in the dependency_is_flagged flag of this variable, as these are likely to be flagged whenever the aircraft is in cloud.

3.27.1 Outputs

• SEA_TWC_021

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: SEA_TWC_021_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 20
- instrument_manufacturer: Science Engineering Associates, Inc.
- instrument_model: WCM-2000
- instrument_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
- long_name: Total water content from the SEA WCM-2000 probe, element 021
- units: g m-3

• SEA_TWC_083

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: SEA_TWC_083_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 20
- instrument_manufacturer: Science Engineering Associates, Inc.
- instrument_model: WCM-2000

- instrument_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
- long_name: Total water content from the SEA WCM-2000 probe, element 083
- units: g m-3
- **SEA_LWC_021**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: SEA_LWC_021_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 20
 - instrument_manufacturer: Science Engineering Associates, Inc.
 - instrument_model: WCM-2000
 - instrument_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
 - long_name: Liquid water content from the SEA WCM-2000 probe, element 021
 - standard_name: mass_concentration_of_liquid_water_in_air
 - units: g m-3
- **SEA_LWC_083**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: SEA_LWC_083_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 20
 - instrument_manufacturer: Science Engineering Associates, Inc.
 - instrument_model: WCM-2000
 - instrument_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
 - long_name: Liquid water content from the SEA WCM-2000 probe, element 083
 - standard_name: mass_concentration_of_liquid_water_in_air
 - units: g m-3

3.27.2 Flags

Variables in this module use bitmask flags. Some, all or none of these flags may be applied to each variable. Interrogate flag variable attributes `flag_masks` and `flag_meanings` to find the flags for each variable.

- `element_temperature_out_of_range` - No flag description provided.
- `aircraft_on_ground` - No flag description provided.

3.28 SignalRegister

`p_signal_register.py`

The DECADES signal register is a packed representation of some boolean state variables, which is used internally in DECADES. Here we reproduce part of the register from flag variables reported in the TCP data, for use in other processing modules. No outputs defined here are expected to ever be written to file.

3.28.1 Outputs

- **SREG**

- `_FillValue`: -9999
- `actual_range`: [`<float32: derived_from_file>`, `<float32: derived_from_file>`]
- `ancillary_variables`: SREG_FLAG
- `coordinates`: `<str: derived_from_file optional>`
- `coverage_content_type`: `physicalMeasurement`
- `frequency`: 2
- `long_name`: Signal Register
- `units`: None

3.28.2 Flags

Variables in this module use classic, value based flagging.

- **SREG_FLAG**

- -128: `data_not_flagged` - A fill value. No flagging information has been provided

3.29 SolarAngles

`p_solar.py`

Calculates solar azimuth and zenith angles at the aircraft location. Uses the third party python module `pysolar`.

3.29.1 Outputs

- **SOL_ZEN**

- `_FillValue`: -9999
- `actual_range`: [`<float32: derived_from_file>`, `<float32: derived_from_file>`]
- `ancillary_variables`: SOL_ZEN_FLAG
- `coordinates`: `<str: derived_from_file optional>`
- `coverage_content_type`: `physicalMeasurement`
- `frequency`: 1
- `long_name`: Solar zenith derived from aircraft position and time
- `standard_name`: `solar_zenith_angle`
- `units`: `degree`

- **SOL_AZIM**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: SOL_AZIM_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 1
- long_name: Solar azimuth derived from aircraft position and time
- standard_name: solar_azimuth_angle
- units: degree

3.29.2 Flags

Variables in this module use classic, value based flagging.

- **SOL_ZEN_FLAG**

- -128: data_not_flagged - A fill value. No flagging information has been provided

- **SOL_AZIM_FLAG**

- -128: data_not_flagged - A fill value. No flagging information has been provided

3.30 TPress

[p_tpress.py](#)

This module calculates turbulence probe pressure differentials between P0-S10, left-right, and up-down.

The raw inputs are DLU counts from the differential pressure transducers. Pressures are calculated with polynomial fits to the raw counts, which encompass both the pressure to volts calibration of the transducer, and the volts to counts calibration of the DLU. These are given in the constant parameters CALTP1, CALTP2, and CALTP3, for P0-S10, up-down, and left right, respectively.

Data are flagged when outside specified limits.

3.30.1 Outputs

- **P0_S10**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: P0_S10_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32
- long_name: Calibrated differential pressure between centre (P0) port and S10 static
- sensor_manufacturer: Rosemount Aerospace. Inc.
- sensor_model: 1221F2
- sensor_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>

- units: hPa

- **PA_TURB**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: PA_TURB_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32
- long_name: Calibrated differential pressure between turbulence probe vertical ports
- sensor_manufacturer: Rosemount Aerospace. Inc.
- sensor_model: 1221F2
- sensor_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
- units: hPa

- **PB_TURB**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: PB_TURB_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32
- long_name: Calibrated differential pressure between turbulence probe horizontal ports
- sensor_manufacturer: Rosemount Aerospace. Inc.
- sensor_model: 1221F2
- sensor_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
- units: hPa

3.30.2 Flags

Variables in this module use classic, value based flagging.

- **P0_S10_FLAG**

- 0: data_good - None
- 1: data_out_of_range - None

- **PA_TURB_FLAG**

- 0: data_good - None
- 1: data_out_of_range - None

- **PB_TURB_FLAG**

- 0: data_good - None
- 1: data_out_of_range - None

3.31 TecoSO2

p_tei_so2.py

Warning

This module deprecated for flights after 2021-01-09

Calculate SO₂ concentration from the TECO 43 instrument. The instrument reports a nominal concentration and sensitivity, valve states V6 (indicating cylinder air) and V8 (indicating cabin air), and a status flag.

Zeros are taken whenever the instrument in sampling cylinder or cabin air, and interpolated back to 1 Hz, assuming a linear drift of the offsets between zeros. SO₂ concentration is then given by

$$[\text{SO}_2] = \frac{[\text{SO}_{2|\text{INS}}] - Z}{S},$$

where $[\text{SO}_{2|\text{INS}}]$ is the concentration reported by the instrument, Z is the zero obtained from sampling cylinder or cabin air, and S is the sensitivity reported by the instrument.

Flagging is based on valve states and the instrument status flag.

3.31.1 Outputs

- **SO2_TECO**
 - `_FillValue`: -9999
 - `actual_range`: [`<float32: derived_from_file>`, `<float32: derived_from_file>`]
 - `ancillary_variables`: SO2_TECO_FLAG
 - `coordinates`: `<str: derived_from_file optional>`
 - `coverage_content_type`: `physicalMeasurement`
 - `frequency`: 1
 - `instrument_manufacturer`: Thermo Fisher Scientific, Inc.
 - `instrument_model`: 43i TLE pulsed fluorescence SO2 spectrometer
 - `long_name`: Mole fraction of Sulphur Dioxide in air from TECO 43 instrument
 - `standard_name`: `mole_fraction_of_sulfur_dioxide_in_air`
 - `units`: ppb

3.31.2 Flags

Variables in this module use bitmask flags. Some, all or none of these flags may be applied to each variable. Interrogate flag variable attributes `flag_masks` and `flag_meanings` to find the flags for each variable.

- `aircraft_on_ground` - Aircraft is on the ground
- `before_first_zero` - The instrument has not yet sampled cylinder or cabin air, the zero is invalid
- `in_zero` - The instrument is currently sampling cylinder or cabin air for a zero reading
- `in_alarm` - The instrument status flag is currently indicating an alarm state

3.32 TecoSO2V2

p_tei_so2_v2.py

Note

This module only active for flights after 2021-01-09

Calculate SO₂ concentration from the TECO 43 instrument.

Zeros are taken whenever valve states V7 or V8 are 1, and are interpolated back to 1 Hz, assuming a linear drift of the offsets between zeros. SO₂ concentration is then given by

$$[\text{SO}_2] = \frac{[\text{SO}_{2|\text{INS}}] - Z}{S},$$

where $[\text{SO}_{2|\text{INS}}]$ is the concentration reported by the instrument, Z is the zero obtained from sampling scrubbed ambient air, and S is the instrument sensitivity given in the flight constants.

Flagging is based on valve states, weight on wheels, and the instrument status flag.

3.32.1 Outputs

• SO2_TECO

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: SO2_TECO_FLAG
- calibration_date: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- calibration_information: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- calibration_url: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 1
- instrument_manufacturer: Thermo Fisher Scientific, Inc.
- instrument_model: 43i Trace Level-Enhanced pulsed fluorescence SO2 spectrometer
- instrument_serial_number: 1505564557
- long_name: Mole fraction of Sulphur Dioxide in air from TECO 43 instrument
- standard_name: mole_fraction_of_sulfur_dioxide_in_air
- units: ppb

• SO2_TECO_ZERO

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- calibration_date: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- calibration_information: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- calibration_url: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>

- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 1
- instrument_manufacturer: Thermo Fisher Scientific, Inc.
- instrument_model: 43i Trace Level-Enhanced pulsed fluorescence SO2 spectrometer
- instrument_serial_number: 1505564557
- long_name: TECO 43 SO2 interpolated zero
- units: ppb

3.32.2 Flags

3.33 TeiOzone

p_teiozone.py

Provides ozone concentration from the TE49C O₃ analyser. Ozone data are taken as-is from the instrument; this module provides flagging information based on threshold values and instrument status flags.

3.33.1 Outputs

- O3_TECO

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: O3_TECO_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 1
- instrument_manufacturer: Thermo Fisher Scientific, Inc.
- instrument_model: 49i IV absorption ozone photometer
- long_name: Mole fraction of Ozone in air from the TECO 49 instrument
- standard_name: mole_fraction_of_ozone_in_air
- units: ppb

3.33.2 Flags

Variables in this module use bitmask flags. Some, all or none of these flags may be applied to each variable. Interrogate flag variable attributes `flag_masks` and `flag_meanings` to find the flags for each variable.

- `instrument_alarm` - The status flag provided by the instrument is indicating an alarm state
- `conc_out_of_range` - Reported ozone concentration is below the valid minimum of -10
- `flow_out_of_range` - At least one of the recorded flow rates is below the valid minimum of 0.5
- `aircraft_on_ground` - The aircraft is on the ground

3.34 ThermistorV1Temperatures

p_thermistor_temps.py

Calculate indicated and true (static) air temperatures from the Rosemount temperature probes, for the V1 (prototype) thermistor circuit. Note that when using this circuit, only one of the housings may host a thermistor type sensor.

- Processes the NPL calibrations to produce a resistance to probe temperature relationship. The NPL calibration is performed with two different applied voltages so that self-heating can be calculated. This allows the probe temperature to be inferred by adding the calibration chamber temperature to the self-heating in order to produce a useable probe temperature to resistance calibration. }
- Processes the NPL calibrations for a temperature to dissipation constant relationship. The dissipation constant measured in the calibration chamber for a given temperature is used later in the removal of self-heating in flight. }
- Calculates the indicated temperature of the thermistor sensor by applying the NPL calibration and the DECADES counts to voltage calibration.
- Calculates the dissipation constant at that indicated temperature based on the calibration dissipation constant and the flight dissipation multiplier (as described in FAAM013004A). }
- Calculates the in-flight self-heating for each measurement, based on the voltage measurements and in-flight dissipation constants. }
- Produces an indicated temperature corrected for self-heating by subtracting the self-heating from the temperature of the sensor. }

The deiced indicated temperature is subject to a heating correction term when the heater is active, given by

$$\Delta T_{IAT} = \frac{1}{10} \exp(\exp(a + (\log(M) + b)(c(q + P) + d))),$$

where M is the Mach number, q is the dynamic pressure and P the static pressure. The parameters a , b , c , and d are

$$[1.171, 2.738, -0.000568, -0.452].$$

True air temperatures are a function of indicated temperatures, Mach number and housing recovery factor, and are given by

$$T_{TAT} = \frac{T_{IAT}}{1 + (0.2R_f M^2)},$$

where M is the Mach number and R_f the recovery factor. Recovery factors are currently considered constant, and are specified in the flight constants parameters RM_RECFACT/DI and RM_RECFACT/ND.

A flag is applied to the data when the Mach number is out of range. **Further flags may be added by standalone flagging modules.**

3.34.1 Outputs

- IAT_ND_R
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: [<float32: derived_from_file>, <float32: derived_from_file>]
 - ancillary_variables: IAT_ND_R_FLAG
 - calibration_date: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - calibration_information: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - calibration_url: <str: derived_from_file optional>

- comment: Sensor housed in Rosemount Aerospace Inc. Type 102 non-deiced Total Temperature Housing
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32
- long_name: Indicated air temperature from the Rosemount non-deiced temperature sensor
- sensor_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
- sensor_type: thermistor
- units: K

- **TAT_ND_R**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: TAT_ND_R_FLAG
- calibration_date: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- calibration_information: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- calibration_url: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- comment: Sensor housed in Rosemount Aerospace Inc. Type 102 non-deiced Total Temperature Housing
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32
- long_name: True air temperature from the Rosemount non-deiced temperature sensor
- sensor_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
- sensor_type: thermistor
- standard_name: air_temperature
- units: K

- **IAT_DI_R**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: IAT_DI_R_FLAG
- calibration_date: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- calibration_information: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- calibration_url: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- comment: Sensor housed in Rosemount Aerospace Inc. Type 102 deiced Total Temperature Housing
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32
- long_name: Indicated air temperature from the Rosemount deiced temperature sensor
- sensor_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>

- sensor_type: thermistor
- units: K
- **TAT_DI_R**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: TAT_DI_R_FLAG
 - calibration_date: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - calibration_information: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - calibration_url: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - comment: Sensor housed in Rosemount Aerospace Inc. Type 102 deiced Total Temperature Housing
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 32
 - long_name: True air temperature from the Rosemount deiced temperature sensor
 - sensor_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
 - sensor_type: thermistor
 - standard_name: air_temperature
 - units: K

3.34.2 Flags

Variables in this module use bitmask flags. Some, all or none of these flags may be applied to each variable. Interrogate flag variable attributes `flag_masks` and `flag_meanings` to find the flags for each variable.

- `mach_out_of_range` - No flag description provided.

3.35 TurbulenceProbe

[p_turbwinds.py](#)

This module produces flow angles and airspeed from the turbulence probe pressure differentials, and combines these with inertial/GPS measurements to derive 3-dimensional winds. These two processes are performed iteratively so that covariances between inferred winds and inertial measurements can be used to calculate on-the-fly flow angle correction terms. Alternatively, flow angle corrections can be provided in the flight constants.

Flow angles, dynamic pressure, and TAS

Initial estimates for angle of attack, α , and angle of sideslip, β , are given by

$$\alpha = (P_a/q - a_0) / a_1,$$

$$\beta = (P_b/q - b_0) / b_1.$$

Here, P_a and P_b are the pressure differentials between the top/bottom and left/right probe ports, a_n and b_n are calibration coefficients derived from flight data, and q is the RVSM-derived dynamic pressure.

Correction terms to these flow angles, required as stagnation points do not correspond exactly with probe ports, calculated by BAeS during the probe commissioning, are given by

$$\delta_\alpha = 0.0273 + \alpha(-0.0141 + \alpha(0.00193 - 0.000052\alpha)),$$

$$\delta_\beta = 0.00076172\beta^2.$$

An initial estimate of dynamic pressure from the turbulence probe, q_t , is then given by

$$q_t = \Delta_{P_0 S_{10}} + q(\delta_\alpha + \delta_\beta),$$

where $\Delta_{P_0 S_{10}}$ is the pressure differential between P_0 and S_{10} .

This whole process is then iteratively repeated with $q = q_t$, either until the difference in both flow angles between iterations is less than 0.2 degrees, or 5 iterations have been completed.

Mach number, M , is given by

$$M = \sqrt{5 \left(\left(1 + \frac{q_t}{p} \right)^{\frac{2}{\gamma}} - 1 \right)},$$

where p is the static pressure from the RVSM system.

True airspeed, TAS, is then given by

$$\text{TAS} = \text{TAS}_c C_0 M \sqrt{T_{\text{air}}/T_0},$$

where TAS_c is a correction term derived from flight data, C_0 is the speed of sound at ICAO STP, T_{air} is the (deiced) true air temperature, and T_0 is the temperature at ICAO STP.

Wind vector

First let us define rotation matrices which provide the transformations between geographical and aircraft-relative coordinate systems.

$$\mathbf{A}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos(r) & -\sin(r) \\ 0 & \sin(r) & \cos(r) \end{bmatrix},$$

$$\mathbf{A}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta) & 0 & -\sin(\theta) \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \sin(\theta) & 0 & \cos(\theta) \end{bmatrix},$$

$$\mathbf{A}_3 = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\phi) & \sin(\phi) & 0 \\ -\sin(\phi) & \cos(\phi) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix},$$

where r , θ , and ϕ are the aircraft roll, pitch, and yaw, respectively. We can combine these into a single transformation tensor, $\mathbf{R} = (\mathbf{A}_3 \cdot \mathbf{A}_2) \cdot \mathbf{A}_1$.

The wind vector \mathbf{U} , is given by

$$\mathbf{U} = \mathbf{V} + \mathbf{T} + \mathbf{L},$$

where \mathbf{V} is the aircraft velocity vector, \mathbf{T} is the aircraft TAS vector, relative to the earth, and \mathbf{L} is a correction term which accounts for the offset between the aircraft inertial measurement and the turbulence probe.

The correction term \mathbf{L} is given by

$$\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{L}_L \times \mathbf{L}_R,$$

where $\mathbf{L}_R = \mathbf{R} \cdot \mathbf{l}$ and $\mathbf{L}_L = \mathbf{L}_1 + \mathbf{L}_2 + \mathbf{L}_3$.

Here \mathbf{l} is the position vector describing the offset of the inertial measurement from the turbulence probe, and

$$\mathbf{L}_1 = [0, 0, -\dot{\phi}],$$

$$\mathbf{L}_2 = \mathbf{A}_3 \cdot [0, \dot{\theta}, 0],$$

$$\mathbf{L}_3 = (\mathbf{A}_3 \cdot \mathbf{A}_2) \cdot [\dot{r}, 0, 0],$$

where an overdot represents a time derivative.

The TAS term T is given by

$$R = \mathbf{R} \cdot [-T_p, -T_p \tan(\beta), T_p \tan(\alpha)],$$

where

$$T_p = \frac{\text{TAS}}{\sqrt{1 + \tan(\beta)^2 + \tan(\alpha)^2}}.$$

Flow angle corrections

The derivation of the variables above assumes no flow angle corrections, which are generally required. We take the approach of calculating flow angle corrections on line. This is done in an iterative loop where, after calculation of the flow angles and wind vector, flow angle corrections are calculated by 1) minimising the covariance between platform roll and vertical wind in the turns, and 2) minimising the mean vertical wind when the platform is straight and level. Flow angles are then recalculated, and so on until the flow angle corrections converge suitably. This has been seen to occur rapidly, and only two iterations after the initial calculations are performed.

3.35.1 Outputs

- TAS

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: TAS_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32
- long_name: True airspeed (dry-air) from turbulence probe
- standard_name: platform_speed_wrt_air
- units: m s-1

- AOA

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: AOA_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32
- long_name: Angle of attack from the turbulence probe (positive, flow upwards wrt a/c axes)
- units: degree

- AOSS

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: AOSS_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32

- long_name: Angle of sideslip from the turbulence probe (positive, flow from left)
- units: degree
- **PSP_TURB**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: PSP_TURB_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 32
 - long_name: Pitot-static pressure from centre-port measurements corrected for AoA and AoSS
 - units: hPa
- **U_C**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: U_C_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 32
 - long_name: Eastward wind component from turbulence probe and GIN
 - standard_name: eastward_wind
 - units: m s-1
- **V_C**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: V_C_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 32
 - long_name: Northward wind component from turbulence probe and GIN
 - standard_name: northward_wind
 - units: m s-1
- **W_C**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: W_C_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 32
 - long_name: Vertical wind component from turbulence probe and GIN

- standard_name: upward_air_velocity
- units: m s⁻¹

3.35.2 Flags

Variables in this module use bitmask flags. Some, all or none of these flags may be applied to each variable. Interrogate flag variable attributes `flag_masks` and `flag_meanings` to find the flags for each variable.

- `data_out_of_range` - V_C is outside the specified valid range [(-60, 60)] m/s
- `aircraft_on_ground` - aircraft on ground
- `mach_out_of_range` - Mach # is outside the specified valid range [(0.05, 0.8)]

3.36 TwoBOzone

`p_2b_ozone.py`

Note

This module only active for flights after 2021-01-09

Provides ozone concentration from the 2B Tech Ozone instrument. The instrument natively provides an ozone concentration, however this may be zero adjusted and scaled by zero and sensitivity parameters given in the flight constants as `TWBOZO_ZERO` and `TWBOZO_SENS`.

$$O_3 = \frac{O_3 - z}{S},$$

where z is the given zero offset and S is the given sensitivity.

Additional calibration information for metadata can be provided through the constant parameters `TWBOZO_CALINFO_DATE`, `TWBOZO_CALINFO_INFO`, and `TWBOZO_CALINFO_URL`.

Flagging information is provided based on instrument and aircraft status.

3.36.1 Outputs

- **O3_2BTECH**
 - `_FillValue`: -9999
 - `actual_range`: [`<float32: derived_from_file>`, `<float32: derived_from_file>`]
 - `ancillary_variables`: O3_2BTECH_FLAG
 - `calibration_date`: `<str: derived_from_file optional>`
 - `calibration_information`: `<str: derived_from_file optional>`
 - `calibration_url`: `<str: derived_from_file optional>`
 - `coordinates`: `<str: derived_from_file optional>`
 - `coverage_content_type`: physicalMeasurement
 - `frequency`: 1
 - `instrument_description`: `<str: derived_from_file optional>`
 - `instrument_manufacturer`: 2B Technologies Inc.
 - `instrument_model`: 205

- instrument_serial_number: 1034DB
- long_name: Mole fraction of Ozone in air from the 2BTech photometer
- standard_name: mole_fraction_of_ozone_in_air
- units: ppb

3.36.2 Flags

Variables in this module use bitmask flags. Some, all or none of these flags may be applied to each variable. Interrogate flag variable attributes `flag_masks` and `flag_meanings` to find the flags for each variable.

- `aircraft_on_ground` - The aircraft is on the ground, as indicated by the weight on wheels flag. An additional 10 seconds are added after take-off to allow for instrument flushing.
- `inlet_flow_out_of_range` - The inlet sample overflow is out of range.
- `sample_flow_out_of_range` - The spectrometer sample mass flow rate is out of range.

3.37 WVSS2A

`p_wvss2.py`

Process data from the WVSS-II water vapour spectrometers. The WVSS2 report volume mixing ratio and other parameters approximately every 2.3 seconds. This represents ~2 s of sampling at ~4 Hz, followed by around 0.3 seconds of processing. This module simply linearly interpolates these data onto a regular 1 Hz index, and provides flagging and metadata.

3.37.1 Outputs

- **WVSS2F_VMR_U**
 - `_FillValue`: -9999
 - `actual_range`: [`<float32: derived_from_file>`, `<float32: derived_from_file>`]
 - `ancillary_variables`: WVSS2F_VMR_U_FLAG
 - `comment`: WVSS-II measurements rely on manufacturer calibrations, and are not traceable to national standards
 - `coordinates`: `<str: derived_from_file optional>`
 - `coverage_content_type`: `physicalMeasurement`
 - `frequency`: 1
 - `instrument_manufacturer`: SpectraSensors
 - `long_name`: Water Vapour Measurement from WVSS2F linearly interpolated to 1 Hz
 - `units`: ppmv
- **WVSS2F_PRESS_U**
 - `_FillValue`: -9999
 - `actual_range`: [`<float32: derived_from_file>`, `<float32: derived_from_file>`]
 - `ancillary_variables`: WVSS2F_PRESS_U_FLAG
 - `comment`: WVSS-II measurements rely on manufacturer calibrations, and are not traceable to national standards
 - `coordinates`: `<str: derived_from_file optional>`

- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 1
- instrument_manufacturer: SpectraSensors
- long_name: Pressure inside WVSS2F sample cell linearly interpolated to 1 Hz
- units: hPa

3.37.2 Flags

Variables in this module use bitmask flags. Some, all or none of these flags may be applied to each variable. Interrogate flag variable attributes `flag_masks` and `flag_meanings` to find the flags for each variable.

- `data_out_of_range` - No flag description provided.
- `data_missing` - No flag description provided.
- `aircraft_on_ground` - No flag description provided.

3.38 WVSS2B

`p_wvss2.py`

Process data from the WVSS-II water vapour spectrometers. The WVSS2 report volume mixing ratio and other parameters approximately every 2.3 seconds. This represents ~2 s of sampling at ~4 Hz, followed by around 0.3 seconds of processing. This module simply linearly interpolates these data onto a regular 1 Hz index, and provides flagging and metadata.

3.38.1 Outputs

- **WVSS2R_VMR_U**
 - `_FillValue`: -9999
 - `actual_range`: [`<float32: derived_from_file>`, `<float32: derived_from_file>`]
 - `ancillary_variables`: WVSS2R_VMR_U_FLAG
 - `comment`: WVSS-II measurements rely on manufacturer calibrations, and are not tracable to national standards
 - `coordinates`: `<str: derived_from_file optional>`
 - `coverage_content_type`: physicalMeasurement
 - `frequency`: 1
 - `instrument_manufacturer`: SpectraSensors
 - `long_name`: Water Vapour Measurement from WVSS2R linearly interpolated to 1 Hz
 - `units`: ppmv
- **WVSS2R_PRESS_U**
 - `_FillValue`: -9999
 - `actual_range`: [`<float32: derived_from_file>`, `<float32: derived_from_file>`]
 - `ancillary_variables`: WVSS2R_PRESS_U_FLAG
 - `comment`: WVSS-II measurements rely on manufacturer calibrations, and are not tracable to national standards
 - `coordinates`: `<str: derived_from_file optional>`

- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 1
- instrument_manufacturer: SpectraSensors
- long_name: Pressure inside WVSS2R sample cell linearly interpolated to 1 Hz
- units: hPa

3.38.2 Flags

Variables in this module use bitmask flags. Some, all or none of these flags may be applied to each variable. Interrogate flag variable attributes `flag_masks` and `flag_meanings` to find the flags for each variable.

- `data_out_of_range` - No flag description provided.
- `data_missing` - No flag description provided.
- `aircraft_on_ground` - No flag description provided.

3.39 WVSS2Calibrated

`p_wvss2_cal.py`

For further details see the [FAAM Met. Handbook](#).

This module provides a calibrated WVSS2 volume mixing ratio, along with its uncertainty estimate, from the flush mounted instrument. The calibration is a polynomial in VMR, with coefficients provided in the constants parameter `WVSS2_F_CAL`. The calibration is assumed to only be valid within a certain VMR range, specified in the constants parameter `WVSS2_F_CAL_RANGE`. Outside of this range, data are set to NaN.

The uncertainty estimate, U_c , is given by

$$U_c = \sqrt{\sigma_f^2 + \sigma_r^2 + \sigma_b^2},$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_f &= \sigma_0 + \sigma_1 V + \dots + \sigma_n V^n \\ \sigma_b &= \frac{l_0 + l_1 V}{2} \\ \sigma_r &= V (p_0 V^{p_1})\end{aligned}$$

where V is the uncorrected volume mixing ratio, $\sigma_0, \dots, \sigma_n$ are specified in the constants parameter `WVSS2_F_UNC_FITPARAMS`, l_0 and l_1 are specified in the constants parameter `WVSS2_F_UNC_BUCK` and p_0 and p_1 are specified in the constants parameter `WVSS2_F_UNC_FITRES`.

3.39.1 Outputs

- `WVSS2F_VMR_C`
 - `_FillValue`: -9999
 - `actual_range`: [`<float32: derived_from_file>`, `<float32: derived_from_file>`]
 - `ancillary_variables`: `WVSS2F_VMR_C_FLAG`
 - `coordinates`: `<str: derived_from_file optional>`
 - `coverage_content_type`: `physicalMeasurement`
 - `frequency`: 1
 - `instrument_manufacturer`: `SpectraSensors`

- instrument_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
- long_name: Calibrated volume mixing ratio from WVSS2F
- units: ppm
- **WVSS2F_VMR_C_CU**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: WVSS2F_VMR_C_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: auxiliaryInformation
 - frequency: 1
 - instrument_manufacturer: SpectraSensors
 - instrument_serial_number: <str: derived_from_file>
 - long_name: Uncertainty estimate for calibrated volume mixing ratio from WVSS2F
 - units: ppm

3.39.2 Flags

3.40 WVSS2RH

p_wvss2_rh.py

This module provides estimates of relative humidity with respect to both water and ice, along with their combined uncertainty estimates, derived from the WVSS2 water vapour mixing ratio and Rosemount temperatures.

For full details of the methodology, see the [FAAM Met. Handbook](#).

3.40.1 Outputs

- **RH_ICE**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: RH_ICE_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
 - frequency: 1
 - long_name: Relative humidity wrt ice water, derived from corrected WVSS-II VMR and Rosemount temperatures
 - standard_name: relative_humidity
 - units: %
- **RH_LIQ**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: RH_LIQ_FLAG

- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 1
- long_name: Relative humidity wrt liquid water, derived from corrected WVSS-II VMR and Rose-mount temperatures
- standard_name: relative_humidity
- units: %
- **RH_ICE_CU**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: RH_ICE_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: auxiliaryInformation
 - frequency: 1
 - long_name: Combined uncertainty estimate for RH_ICE
 - units: %
- **RH_LIQ_CU**
 - _FillValue: -9999
 - actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
 - ancillary_variables: RH_LIQ_FLAG
 - coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
 - coverage_content_type: auxiliaryInformation
 - frequency: 1
 - long_name: Combined uncertainty estimate for RH_LIQ
 - units: %

3.40.2 Flags

3.41 WeightOnWheels

`p_wow.py`

This module simply provides the aircraft weight-on-wheels flag, recorded on the rear core console. A value of 1 indicates weight on wheels (i.e. the aircraft is on the ground) and a value of 0 indicates no weight on wheels (i.e. the aircraft is airborne).

3.41.1 Outputs

- **WOW_IND**

- `_FillValue`: -9999
- `actual_range`: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- `coordinates`: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- `coverage_content_type`: physicalMeasurement
- `frequency`: 1
- `long_name`: Weight on wheels indicator
- `units`: 1

3.41.2 Flags

3.42 WetMach

`p_wet_mach.py`

This module calculate a moist-air Mach number using RVSM pressure measurements and the volume mixing ratio from the flush mounted WVSSII (assumed to identify itself as WVSS2A).

Moist-air Mach number, M , is given by

$$M = \sqrt{\left(\frac{2c_v}{R_a}\right) \left(\left(\frac{p+q}{q}\right)^{\frac{R_a}{c_p}} - 1\right)},$$

where

$$R_a = c_p - c_v$$

and

$$c_p = c_{pd} \left(1 + q_h \left(\frac{8}{7\epsilon} - 1\right)\right)$$

$$c_v = c_{vd} \left(1 + q_h \left(\frac{6}{5\epsilon} - 1\right)\right)$$

Here c_{pd} and c_{vd} are specific heats for dry air at constant pressure and volume, respectively, ϵ is the ratio of the molecular mass of water to that of dry air, and the specific humidity, q_h , is given by

$$q_h = \frac{\epsilon V}{\epsilon V + 1},$$

where $V = 1000000 \times \text{vmr}_{\text{WVSS2F}}$.

The module also provides the parameter `SH_GAMMA`, which is the ratio of specific heats at constant pressure and constant volume, along with uncertainty estimates for `MACH` and `SH_GAMMA`. The former is a combination from uncertainties in the corrected WVSS2 VMR and the uncertainty reported in BAe Reoprt 126, while the latter arises from the uncertainty in the corrected WVSS2 VMR.

3.42.1 Outputs

- **MACH**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: MACH_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32
- long_name: Moist air Mach derived from WVSS-II(F) and RVSM
- units: 1

- **SH_GAMMA**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: SH_GAMMA_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: physicalMeasurement
- frequency: 32
- long_name: Ratio of specific heats at constant pressure and constant pressure
- units: 1

- **SH_GAMMA_CU**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: SH_GAMMA_CU_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: auxiliaryInformation
- frequency: 32
- long_name: Uncertainty estimate for SH_GAMMA
- units: 1

- **MACH_CU**

- _FillValue: -9999
- actual_range: ['<float32: derived_from_file>', '<float32: derived_from_file>']
- ancillary_variables: MACH_CU_FLAG
- coordinates: <str: derived_from_file optional>
- coverage_content_type: auxiliaryInformation
- frequency: 32
- long_name: Uncertainty estimate for moist-air Mach
- units: 1

3.42.2 Flags

Variables in this module use bitmask flags. Some, all or none of these flags may be applied to each variable. Interrogate flag variable attributes `flag_masks` and `flag_meanings` to find the flags for each variable.

- `aircraft_on_ground` - The aircraft is on the ground, as indicated by the weight-on-wheels indicator

FLAGGING MODULES

Flagging modules run after the main processing jobs are complete, and provide further flagging information to variables. This may be required where the input information cannot be guaranteed to exist due to variations in the aircraft fit. Therefore, the flags provided by these standalone flagging modules may or may not be present in the data.

4.1 RosemountTempDeltaFlag

This class adds a flag to the rosemount temperatures if the two temperatures disagree by more than a given absolute value. This is given by the module constant `TEMPERATURE_THRESHOLD`.

4.1.1 Flagged variable: *TAT_DI_R*

- `discrepancy_threshold_exceeded` - The discrepancy between the deiced and non-deiced temperature sensors is greater than 1.0 K.

4.1.2 Flagged variable: *TAT_ND_R*

- `discrepancy_threshold_exceeded` - The discrepancy between the deiced and non-deiced temperature sensors is greater than 1.0 K.

4.2 RosemountTempCloudFlag

This class adds a flag to all rosemount temperature variables if the aircraft is in cloud, as indicated by `NV_CLEAR_AIR_MASK`, derived from the Nevzorov probe.

4.2.1 Flagged variable: *TAT_DI_R*

- `in_cloud` - The aircraft is indicated as being in cloud, according to the clear air mask derived from the Nevzorov power variance.

4.2.2 Flagged variable: *TAT_ND_R*

- *in_cloud* - The aircraft is indicated as being in cloud, according to the clear air mask derived from the Nevzorov power variance.

4.3 CPCCloudFlag

This class adds a flag to all rosemount temperature variables if the aircraft is in cloud, as indicated by *NV_CLEAR_AIR_MASK*, derived from the Nevzorov probe. Before application, the *NV_CLEAR_AIR_MASK* is shifted by *CPC_LAG_SECS* seconds to account for the time lag between the Nevzorov (considered the reference instrument) and the CPC.

4.3.1 Flagged variable: *CPC_CNTP*

- *in_cloud* - The aircraft is indicated as being in cloud, according to the clear air mask derived from the Nevzorov power variance.

4.4 NephelometerCloudFlag

This class adds a flag to nephelometer scattering data if the aircraft is in cloud, as indicated by *NV_CLEAR_AIR_MASK*, derived from the Nevzorov probe.

4.4.1 Flagged variable: *TSC_BLUU*

- *in_cloud* - The aircraft is indicated as being in cloud, according to the clear air mask derived from the Nevzorov power variance.

4.4.2 Flagged variable: *TSC_GRNU*

- *in_cloud* - The aircraft is indicated as being in cloud, according to the clear air mask derived from the Nevzorov power variance.

4.4.3 Flagged variable: *TSC_REDU*

- *in_cloud* - The aircraft is indicated as being in cloud, according to the clear air mask derived from the Nevzorov power variance.

4.4.4 Flagged variable: *BSC_BLUU*

- *in_cloud* - The aircraft is indicated as being in cloud, according to the clear air mask derived from the Nevzorov power variance.

4.4.5 Flagged variable: *BSC_GRNU*

- *in_cloud* - The aircraft is indicated as being in cloud, according to the clear air mask derived from the Nevzorov power variance.

4.4.6 Flagged variable: *BSC_REDU*

- *in_cloud* - The aircraft is indicated as being in cloud, according to the clear air mask derived from the Nevzorov power variance.

4.5 WVSS2RHTemperatureFlag

This class flags the WVSS-II derived relative humidity wherever the de-iced temperature is flagged. This is now depreciated, as this information is now provided by the *dependency_is_flagged* flag, and may be removed in a future release.

4.5.1 Flagged variable: *RH_ICE*

- *temperature_flagged* - The input temperature measurement has a non-zero flag value

4.5.2 Flagged variable: *RH_LIQ*

- *temperature_flagged* - The input temperature measurement has a non-zero flag value

4.6 WVSS2CloudFlag

This class adds a flag to (uncorrected) WVSS-II volume mixing ratios if the aircraft is in cloud, as indicated by *NV_CLEAR_AIR_MASK*, derived from the Nevzorov probe.

4.6.1 Flagged variable: *WVSS2F_VMR_U*

- *in_cloud* - The aircraft is indicated as being in cloud, according to the clear air mask derived from the Nevzorov power variance.

4.6.2 Flagged variable: *WVSS2R_VMR_U*

- *in_cloud* - The aircraft is indicated as being in cloud, according to the clear air mask derived from the Nevzorov power variance.